

Towards a Continuous-Wave VUV Laser for Thorium-229m Nuclear Clock

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Certificate of Examination

This is to certify that the dissertation titled **Towards a Continuous-Wave VUV Laser for Thorium-229m Nuclear Clock** submitted by **Nutan Kumari Sah** (MS20168) for the partial fulfillment of BS- MS Dual Degree programme of the institute, has been examined by the thesis committee duly appointed by the institute. The committee finds the work done by the candidate satisfactory and recommends that the report be accepted.

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Declaration

The work presented in this dissertation has been carried out by me under the guidance of Dr. Lars von der Wense from Institut für Physik - Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz and Dr. Kamal Priya Singh at the Department of Physical Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Mohali.

This work has not been submitted in part or in full for a degree, a diploma, or a fellowship to any other university or institute. Whenever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions. This thesis is a bonafide record of original work done by me and all sources listed within have been detailed in the bibliography.

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In my capacity as the supervisor of the candidates project work, I certify that the above statements by the candidate are true to the best of my knowledge.

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Abstract

A low-energy nuclear transition in thorium-229, occurring at 148.3 nm in the vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) range, is the only known transition suitable for constructing a nuclear optical clock, offering exceptional prospects for timekeeping and fundamental physics. Recent experiments have demonstrated excitation of the isomeric transition using pulsed lasers and, more recently, a frequency comb. Pulsed lasers provide high pulse energies but have broad linewidths, resulting in both low VUV power spectral density and insufficient resolution for high-precision spectroscopy. Frequency combs, on the other hand, offer narrow linewidths and have recently enabled the first demonstration of a nuclear clock in a solid-state environment (Zhang et al., 2024). The available power per comb mode was 1 nW in this experiment, which is sufficient for exciting the transition in a solid-state environment where billions of atoms are excited simultaneously. However, for single-ion experiments, where the signal is much weaker, higher optical power is desirable. To achieve higher optical power suitable for single-ion experiments, a continuous-wave (cw) VUV laser is suitable. A cw laser not only allows increased VUV power, but also is technologically simpler, more robust, and hence more cost-effective. This research focuses on key aspects of cw VUV laser development, particularly in exploring second-harmonic generation (SHG) via order-disorder poling. Phase matching through order-disorder poling is investigated in a non-linear crystal, Barium Magnesium Tetrafluoride (BMF), to assess its potential for achieving SHG at 148.3 nm. Additionally, an optical cavity is stabilized using the Hänsch-Couillaud technique to enhance SHG, with performance characterized through incoupling efficiency, and enhancement factor measurements. A dedicated VUV detection system, incorporating a photomultiplier tube and a single photon counter, is assembled to monitor and analyze the generated VUV light. By addressing these technical challenges, this work supports ongoing efforts toward realizing a cw VUV source suitable for excitation of the thorium-229m transition in single ion experiments.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 From Atomic Clocks to Nuclear Clocks

Accurate timekeeping has been a cornerstone of scientific and technological progress, enabling advancements in global positioning systems (GPS), fundamental physics tests, and international time standards. The evolution of timekeeping devices has followed a trajectory from mechanical clocks to quartz oscillators and, ultimately, atomic clocks, which provide the highest precision currently available. Atomic clocks operate by exploiting the stable transition frequencies of atoms, typically in the microwave or optical domain. The cesium atomic clock, which defines the SI second, relies on the hyperfine transition of cesium-133 at 9.19 GHz. More recent advancements, such as optical lattice clocks using strontium or ytterbium, offer improved stability and accuracy by utilizing transitions in the optical range[Ludlow 15].

Atomic clocks have revolutionized timekeeping, achieving remarkable precision by exploiting stable electronic transitions. Nevertheless, the quest for even greater accuracy continues, as atomic clocks remain susceptible to external perturbations such as magnetic and electric field fluctuations. One promising approach to overcoming this challenge is the development of nuclear clocks. Nuclear clocks will be less susceptible to electric and magnetic fields due to smaller multipole moments[Peik 03].

Nuclear clocks take advantage of nuclear rather than electronic transitions, offering reduced sensitivity to environmental disturbances. Unlike atomic energy levels, which are affected by electromagnetic interactions with the surroundings, nuclear transitions occur on a much smaller spatial scale within the nucleus, making them inherently more stable. This intrinsic robustness makes nuclear clocks promising candidates for achieving unprecedented precision in timekeeping. In addition to their precision, nuclear clocks offer a unique advantage in probing new physics. In particular, the transition frequency of the $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$ nuclear clock is predicted to be highly sensitive to variations in the fine-structure constant α and

the strong interaction coupling constant α_s [Flambaum 06]. Such enhanced sensitivity increases the discovery potential for phenomena that may manifest as temporal or spatial variation of fundamental constants such as ultralight dark matter [Arvanitaki 15, Stadnik 15]. For a more detailed discussion, the reader is referred to the review [Thirolf 19].

The realization of a nuclear clock relies on the existence of a nuclear transition with sufficiently low energy to allow laser-based interrogation. The only known transition meeting this criterion is the isomeric state of thorium-229 ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}$), which was first proposed as a candidate for a nuclear clock transition in 2003 [Peik 03]. Recent advances in precision spectroscopy and laser technology have brought this concept closer to realization, allowing nuclear clocks to complement atomic clocks in pushing the boundaries of metrology and fundamental physics.

1.2 Thorium-229: The Ideal Candidate

Before we start it is important to note that this is not an exhaustive account of the developments related to thorium-229 and its nuclear isomer. Here, I will focus on the major breakthroughs that paved the way for nuclear clock development. For a more comprehensive overview of the topic, the reader is referred to several thorough review articles [Thirolf 24, von der Wense 20, Peik 20].

Thorium-229 is the only known nucleus that exhibits a metastable excited state (isomer) at an energy low enough to be accessed with existing laser technology. Unlike atomic transitions, which typically have energies on the order of a few eV, nuclear transitions generally lie in the keV to MeV range, making direct laser excitation impractical. However, in 1976, decay spectroscopy studies of ^{233}U provided evidence for an unusually low-energy nuclear transition in ^{229}Th , estimated to be below 100 eV [Kroger 76].

Subsequent advancements in experimental techniques led to refined energy estimates. In 1994, an indirect measurement reported an excitation energy of 3.4 ± 1 eV [Helmer 94], positioning the transition within the optical domain. This remarkable finding sparked interest in potential applications, and in 2003, the idea of using the thorium-229 isomeric transition to develop a nuclear clock, highlighting its potential for unprecedented timekeeping stability was proposed [Peik 03].

In 2007, a microcalorimetric measurement suggested a revised energy of 7.5 ± 0.5 eV [Beck 07], firmly placing it within the VUV range accessible through high harmonic generation and four-wave mixing for laser spectroscopy. Motivated by this, a proposal was made to develop a single-ion nuclear clock utilizing the nuclear magnetic-dipole transition of the thorium-229 isomer. This clock was predicted to have a projected fractional inaccuracy approaching 1×10^{-19} [Campbell 12].

However, until this point, all energy values were derived indirectly. A major breakthrough occurred in 2016 when the first direct detection of the thorium-229 isomeric transition was achieved via the internal conversion (IC) decay channel, laying the foundation for precise studies of its decay parameters, which are essential for its direct optical excitation [von der Wense 16].

Figure 1.1: Comparison of nuclear transition energies across various nuclei, highlighting the unique low-energy regime occupied by the thorium-229 isomer. The exceptionally low transition energy of thorium-229 makes it well-suited for laser-based spectroscopy. Adapted from [Thirolf 24]

The isomeric state of thorium-229 can decay through three possible channels: internal conversion, bound internal conversion, and radiative decay. In internal conversion (IC), the nucleus transfers its energy to an atomic electron, which is then ejected. In bound internal conversion (BIC), this energy transfer promotes an electron to a higher bound state instead of ejecting it. This excited electron then returns to the ground state by emitting one or more photons. Radiative decay involves the direct emission of a photon from the nucleus. In 2017, the lifetime of the internal conversion decay channel in case of the neutral thorium was measured [Seiferle 17]. A precise determination of the transition energy followed in 2019, yielding a value of 8.28 ± 0.17 eV [Seiferle 19]. An additional breakthrough came in 2023 when the radiative decay channel was directly observed at the ISOLDE facility at CERN, achieving unprecedented precision in the transition energy measurement of 8.338 ± 0.024 eV [Kraemer 22]. These milestones have solidified thorium-229 as an ideal

candidate for a nuclear clock, offering a unique combination of low transition energy and long isomeric lifetime. As shown in Fig. 1.1, the thorium-229 isomer stands out among nuclear transitions by occupying a unique low-energy regime, making it exceptionally suited for laser-based spectroscopy.

1.3 Laser Excitation of the Thorium-229 Isomer in 2024

Following the direct detection of the thorium-229 isomeric transition, significant progress has been made in its spectroscopy. The primary goal has been to achieve controlled laser excitation of this transition, a necessary step toward realizing a nuclear clock. In 2024, three independent research groups successfully demonstrated laser excitation of the isomeric state, marking a major breakthrough in nuclear clock research.

Researchers at PTB and TU Wien achieved the first successful laser excitation of the thorium-229 isomer using a tunable VUV laser system. By doping thorium-229 into CaF_2 crystals, they observed a resonance fluorescence signal at 148.3821 nm. Unlike atomic transitions, which are highly sensitive to the electronic environment and therefore unsuitable for solid-state operation, nuclear transitions are largely shielded from external perturbations. This makes nuclear clocks viable in solid-state environments. The measured fluorescence lifetime of 630 seconds corresponds to an isomer half-life of approximately 1740 seconds in vacuum, demonstrating the feasibility of laser spectroscopy for nuclear state manipulation and paving the way toward optical nuclear clocks [Tiedau 24].

Shortly after, researchers at UCLA achieved laser excitation of thorium-229 doped into a LiSrAlF_6 crystal. The experiment identified a narrow spectral feature at 148.382 nm, which was assigned to the isomeric transition. The observed transition lifetime was consistent with theoretical expectations, further confirming the viability of laser spectroscopy for nuclear state manipulation [Elwell 24]. Both of these experiments employed broadband pulsed laser systems leading to low VUV power spectral density and limited resolution for high-precision spectroscopy.

The most recent study came from JILA, where researchers utilized a vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) frequency comb to directly excite the thorium-229 isomeric transition embedded in a CaF_2 host material. Owing to the narrow linewidth of the frequency comb, the experiment enabled high-resolution spectroscopy of the transition and is considered the first demonstration of a nuclear optical clock. This study not only demonstrated controlled laser excitation but also established a direct frequency link between the nuclear transition and an optical atomic clock (the ^{87}Sr clock), providing an essential foundation for all future comparisons of nuclear and atomic clocks [Zhang 24].

These independent confirmations of laser-driven nuclear excitation represent a crucial

milestone in the field. However, pulsed lasers has broad linewidths which causes low VUV power spectral density and is not suitable for high-precision spectroscopy. Frequency combs, on the other hand, offer narrow linewidths and have recently enabled the first demonstration of a nuclear clock in a solid state environment. The available power per comb mode was 1 nW in this experiment, which is sufficient for exciting the transition in a solid-state environment where billions of atoms are excited simultaneously. However, for single-ion experiments, where the signal is much weaker, higher optical power is desirable. To achieve higher optical power, a continuous-wave (cw) VUV laser is suitable. A cw laser not only allows increased VUV power, but also is technologically simpler, more robust, and hence more cost-effective.

1.4 Scope of This Work

This thesis focuses on the development of a continuous-wave (cw) vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) laser at 148.3 nm for precision spectroscopy of the thorium-229 nuclear isomeric transition. The research is structured into three key areas: exploring order-disorder poling for second-harmonic generation (SHG), optical cavity locking for SHG enhancement, and VUV detection.

A novel approach to quasi-phase matching, known as order-disorder poling, is investigated in BMF crystals as a potential technique to achieve SHG at 148.3 nm. An optical cavity is stabilized using the Hänsch-Couillaud locking technique to enhance SHG efficiency, with performance characterized through incoupling efficiency and enhancement factor measurements. Additionally, a VUV detection system, incorporating a photomultiplier tube and a single photon counter, is assembled to monitor and analyze the generated VUV light.

By addressing these key aspects, this work contributes to the broader effort of enabling high-precision nuclear spectroscopy and advancing the realization of a nuclear clock.

Chapter 2

Second Harmonic Generation

2.1 Introduction

The generation of higher-energy photons from lower-energy photons via nonlinear optical materials is a fundamental technique in modern optics. This method, known as second-harmonic generation (SHG), has been extensively utilized to extend the wavelength coverage of laser sources, particularly in the ultraviolet (UV) region. SHG plays a crucial role in applications such as high-resolution spectroscopy, lithography, and precision metrology, where access to shorter wavelengths is essential. To name just a few, continuous-wave ultraviolet output at 385 nm has been realized through intra-cavity second-harmonic generation in diode-pumped Alexandrite lasers [Xiao 24]. Additionally, frequency-tripled Nd:YAG lasers have been widely used to generate 355 nm UV femtosecond pulses by employing cascaded nonlinear conversion stages [Zhang 20]. These examples highlight the versatility and effectiveness of SHG in accessing wavelengths that are otherwise difficult to achieve with conventional laser gain media.

Despite the widespread success of SHG-based sources in the UV range, generating coherent light at even shorter wavelengths—particularly below 150 nm—remains a significant challenge. The primary limitation arises from the non-availability of suitable nonlinear optical materials. For efficient SHG, a material must exhibit high nonlinear coefficients, low absorption at both the fundamental and second-harmonic wavelengths, and allow for phase matching which is necessary for efficient SHG. However, most common nonlinear crystals such as BBO exhibit strong absorption below 190 nm due to the presence of oxygen [Nikogosyan 91], making them unsuitable for generating vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) radiation. Additionally, achieving phase matching in the deep UV and VUV regions is difficult due to material dispersion, which prevents the necessary phase velocity conditions from being met. To date, the shortest wavelength obtained via phase-matched SHG in solid-state nonlinear crystals is 149.8 nm [Nakazato 16].

Among the few materials that exhibit promising properties for VUV generation, barium magnesium tetrafluoride (BaMgF_4 , BMF) has emerged as one of the most viable candidates [Buchter 01]. BMF is transparent well into the VUV region and possesses favorable phase-matching characteristics for SHG [Villora 09]. Furthermore, it offers the potential for quasi-phase matching through periodic poling, which is essential for efficient SHG [Herr 23].

However, achieving the required sub-micron poling periods in BMF for VUV generation presents a significant challenge since issues such as domain merging and fabrication imperfections become more pronounced at such length scales, making precise domain engineering difficult [Mason 02]. One possible approach to overcoming this limitation might be order-disorder poling, a technique that has the potential to modify the nonlinear properties of the crystal in a controlled manner. In this work, we conduct an initial investigation into order-disorder poling in BMF, exploring its feasibility as a means to achieve the necessary periodic structuring for SHG. While this study represents only a preliminary step, and considerable work remains before any definitive conclusions can be drawn, it contributes to the broader ongoing efforts toward realizing a continuous-wave laser at 148.3 nm.

To provide a foundation for understanding our approach, the next subsection introduces the theoretical framework of second-harmonic generation, covering phase matching and quasi-phase matching concepts. Following this, we present our preliminary results on order-disorder poling in BMF and discuss its potential implications for achieving efficient SHG in the VUV region.

2.2 Theory of Second-Harmonic Generation

2.2.1 Nonlinear Optical Response

This section is mainly based on [New 11], unless stated otherwise. In nonlinear optics, the interaction of intense electromagnetic fields with a medium induces polarization beyond the linear regime. The transition from a linear to a nonlinear optical response can be visualized in Fig. 2.1, which illustrates how the induced dipole moment becomes increasingly distorted at higher electric field strengths, leading to the generation of higher harmonics. The total polarization \mathbf{P} in a dielectric material can be expressed as a power series in terms of the electric field \mathbf{E} :

$$\mathbf{P} = \epsilon_0 \left(\chi^{(1)} \mathbf{E} + \chi^{(2)} \mathbf{E}^2 + \chi^{(3)} \mathbf{E}^3 + \dots \right), \quad (2.1)$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, $\chi^{(1)}$ is the linear susceptibility responsible for standard refraction, $\chi^{(2)}$ governs second-order nonlinear effects such as second-harmonic

generation (SHG), and $\chi^{(3)}$ corresponds to third-order effects such as self-focusing and four-wave mixing.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the nonlinear optical response. For weak electric fields (left), the induced dipole moment oscillates sinusoidally with the driving field, corresponding to the linear regime. For strong electric fields (right), the induced polarization becomes nonlinear and contains a superposition of higher harmonics, giving rise to phenomena such as second-harmonic generation. This behavior reflects the power series expansion of polarization in terms of the electric field: $P = \epsilon_0 \left(\chi^{(1)}E + \chi^{(2)}E^2 + \chi^{(3)}E^3 + \dots \right)$.

2.2.2 Origin of Second-Harmonic Generation

For a material with a nonzero second-order susceptibility $\chi^{(2)}$, a fundamental wave at frequency ω induces a nonlinear polarization at twice the frequency, 2ω . If an incident electric field is represented as:

$$\mathbf{E}(t) = E_0 e^{-i\omega t} + \text{c.c.}, \quad (2.2)$$

where c.c. denotes the complex conjugate, the second-order polarization responsible for SHG is given by:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(2)}(2\omega) = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E^2 e^{-i2\omega t} + \text{c.c.} \quad (2.3)$$

This oscillating polarization at 2ω acts as a source term, generating radiation at the second-harmonic frequency.

2.2.3 Quantitative Analysis of Second-Harmonic Generation

To better understand the efficiency of second-harmonic generation (SHG), we now turn to a quantitative description based on Maxwell's equations in a nonlinear medium. Assuming

a non-magnetic, source-free medium with a second-order nonlinear susceptibility $\chi^{(2)}$, the driven wave equation for the second-harmonic field becomes:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_{2\omega} - \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}_{2\omega}}{\partial t^2} = \mu_0 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{P}^{(2)}(2\omega)}{\partial t^2}, \quad (2.4)$$

where the nonlinear polarization $\mathbf{P}^{(2)}(2\omega)$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(2)}(2\omega) = \epsilon_0 \chi^{(2)} E^2 e^{-i2\omega t} + \text{c.c.} \quad (2.5)$$

Assuming plane-wave propagation along the z -axis, using the slowly-varying envelope approximation and assuming no pump depletion, the spatial evolution of the second-harmonic field can be written as:

$$\frac{dE_{2\omega}}{dz} = i\kappa E_{\omega}^2 e^{i\Delta k z}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\kappa \propto \chi^{(2)}$ is a coupling constant, and the phase mismatch Δk is defined as:

$$\Delta k = 2k_{\omega} - k_{2\omega}. \quad (2.7)$$

Integrating this equation over the length L of the nonlinear medium, the intensity of the generated second-harmonic wave becomes:

$$I_{2\omega}(L) \propto \left| \int_0^L e^{i\Delta k z} dz \right|^2 = \left| \frac{\sin(\Delta k L/2)}{\Delta k/2} \right|^2 \propto \text{sinc}^2 \left(\frac{\Delta k L}{2} \right). \quad (2.8)$$

This result highlights the critical role of phase matching. When $\Delta k = 0$, the generated second-harmonic field grows constructively along the propagation direction, resulting in a quadratic increase in intensity with length. In contrast, for $\Delta k \neq 0$, the second-harmonic field experiences periodic oscillations in amplitude, reducing the net conversion efficiency over long distances.

2.3 Nonlinear Coefficients and Susceptibility Tensor Formalism

The second-order susceptibility $\chi^{(2)}$ is a rank-3 tensor that connects the second-order polarization $P_i^{(2)}$ to the electric field components E_j and E_k via:

$$P_i^{(2)} = \epsilon_0 \sum_{j,k} \chi_{ijk}^{(2)} E_j E_k. \quad (2.9)$$

Here, $i, j, k \in \{x, y, z\}$, and $\chi_{ijk}^{(2)}$ characterizes the nonlinear optical response of the crystal along various directions. Due to symmetry and the Kleinman conditions, this third-rank tensor is often reduced and represented using a d -matrix notation:

$$d_{il} \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} \chi_{ijk}^{(2)}, \quad (2.10)$$

where $l \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ corresponds to contracted indices under the assumption of index symmetry $j \leftrightarrow k$. The mapping is typically defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} l = 1 &\rightarrow (j, k) = (x, x), \\ l = 2 &\rightarrow (y, y), \\ l = 3 &\rightarrow (z, z), \\ l = 4 &\rightarrow (y, z) + (z, y), \\ l = 5 &\rightarrow (x, z) + (z, x), \\ l = 6 &\rightarrow (x, y) + (y, x). \end{aligned}$$

The second-order nonlinear polarization vector $\mathbf{P}^{(2)}$ can be expressed using the contracted d -tensor formalism as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} P_x^{(2)} \\ P_y^{(2)} \\ P_z^{(2)} \end{pmatrix} = 2\epsilon_0 \begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{13} & d_{14} & d_{15} & d_{16} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} & d_{23} & d_{24} & d_{25} & d_{26} \\ d_{31} & d_{32} & d_{33} & d_{34} & d_{35} & d_{36} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_x^2 \\ E_y^2 \\ E_z^2 \\ 2E_y E_z \\ 2E_x E_z \\ 2E_x E_y \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.11)$$

The elements d_{ij} of this matrix are referred to as the nonlinear coefficients of the material. These are experimentally measurable quantities that describe the strength of the nonlinear interaction for different field configurations. In practical SHG setups, it is common to define a scalar effective nonlinear coefficient d_{eff} , which represents the projection of the nonlinear tensor interaction onto the particular polarization directions of the interacting waves.

$$d_{\text{eff}} = \sum_{i,j,k} \chi_{ijk}^{(2)} e_i^{(2\omega)} e_j^{(\omega)} e_k^{(\omega)}, \quad (2.12)$$

where $\mathbf{e}^{(\omega)}$ and $\mathbf{e}^{(2\omega)}$ denote the unit polarization vectors of the fundamental and second-harmonic waves, respectively.

2.3.1 Phase Matching in SHG

As we saw in previous subsection efficient SHG requires constructive interference of the generated second-harmonic wave over the interaction length. This condition is fulfilled when the phase velocities of the fundamental and second-harmonic waves are equal, i.e., when the phase-matching condition is satisfied:

$$k_{2\omega} = 2k_{\omega}, \quad (2.13)$$

where k_{ω} and $k_{2\omega}$ are the wavevectors of the fundamental and second-harmonic waves, respectively. which implies that the phase mismatch

$$\Delta k = k_{2\omega} - 2k_{\omega} = 0. \quad (2.14)$$

Since the wavevector k is related to the refractive index n and the wavelength λ as:

$$k = \frac{2\pi n}{\lambda}, \quad (2.15)$$

the wavevectors for the fundamental and second-harmonic waves become:

$$k_{\omega} = \frac{2\pi n_{\omega}}{\lambda_{\omega}} \quad (2.16)$$

$$k_{2\omega} = \frac{2\pi n_{2\omega}}{\lambda_{2\omega}} \quad (2.17)$$

Since $\lambda_{2\omega} = \frac{\lambda_{\omega}}{2}$, the phase-matching condition can be written as:

$$\frac{2\pi n_{2\omega}}{\frac{\lambda_{\omega}}{2}} = 2 \times \frac{2\pi n_{\omega}}{\lambda_{\omega}} \quad (2.18)$$

This simplifies to:

$$n_{2\omega} = n_{\omega} \quad (2.19)$$

Hence, phase matching is achieved when the refractive indices of the fundamental and second-harmonic waves are equal. If this condition is not met, destructive interference leads to limited conversion efficiency. Figure 2.2 shows schematically the constructive and destructive interference in the cases of phase matching and phase mismatching, respectively.

Birefringent Phase Matching

In practice, finding a material with equal refractive indices for both the fundamental and second-harmonic wavelengths is not possible due to the presence of dispersion in materials.

(a) Phase matched (constructive interference)

(b) Phase mismatched (destructive interference)

Figure 2.2: Illustration of the effect of phase matching on second-harmonic generation (SHG). (a) In the phase-matched case ($\Delta k = 0$), the generated second-harmonic waves at different positions within the nonlinear crystal remain in phase and add constructively, resulting in a coherent buildup of SHG intensity along the propagation direction. (b) In the phase-mismatched case ($\Delta k \neq 0$), the generated second-harmonic waves become out of phase due to wavevector mismatch, leading to periodic oscillations between constructive and destructive interference. This behavior is quantitatively described by the $\text{sinc}^2(\Delta kL/2)$ dependence of the SHG intensity shown in Equation (2.8).

However, birefringent materials can solve this issue by utilizing the difference between the ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices.

In a birefringent crystal, the refractive index for ordinary (n_o) and extraordinary (n_e) polarized light can differ significantly. Birefringent phase matching is achieved when the ordinary refractive index at one wavelength equals the extraordinary refractive index at the other wavelength:

$$n_e(\omega) = n_o(2\omega) \quad (2.20)$$

Figure 2.3 illustrates this principle, showing how the refractive indices of fundamental and second-harmonic waves intersect under birefringent conditions.

Figure 2.3: Wavelength-dependent refractive index curves for the ordinary and extraordinary polarization in a birefringent crystal. Birefringent phase matching is achieved when the phase velocities of the fundamental and second-harmonic waves are equal, which can be achieved if $n_e(\omega) = n_o(2\omega)$. This is illustrated in the figure where the refractive index of the extraordinary wave at the fundamental frequency matches that of the ordinary wave at the second-harmonic frequency. By tuning the propagation angle relative to the optical axis, the effective refractive index for the extraordinary wave can be controlled, allowing phase matching despite the material dispersion.

While birefringent phase matching has proven effective for many SHG processes, it becomes unfeasible at wavelengths as short as 148.3 nm. Due to the lack of suitable birefringent crystals that support birefringent phase matching at this wavelength, alternative techniques such as quasi-phase matching (QPM) must be considered.

Quasi-Phase Matching (QPM): In materials where birefringent phase matching is impractical, efficient second-harmonic generation (SHG) can still be achieved through Quasi-Phase Matching (QPM). Since this technique doesn't put any constraints on polarization, it allows us to use the highest second-order nonlinear coefficient. This technique compensates for the phase mismatch between the fundamental and second-harmonic waves by periodically inverting the sign of the nonlinear susceptibility, typically through periodic poling, due to which an extra phase is introduced in the system that compensates for the phase mismatch arising from dispersion.

To understand how QPM works, we introduce the concept of *coherence length* (l_c), which is defined as the distance over which the accumulated phase difference between the fundamental and second-harmonic waves reaches 2π , i.e.,

$$l_c = \frac{2\pi}{\Delta k}, \quad (2.21)$$

where $\Delta k = k_{2\omega} - 2k_\omega$ is the wavevector mismatch. Over one coherence length, the second-harmonic field undergoes a full oscillation cycle due to this phase mismatch. The SHG amplitude initially grows due to constructive interference, but as the waves drift out of phase, energy begins to flow back from the second-harmonic wave to the fundamental. As a result, the average SHG efficiency over distances longer than l_c diminishes due to this periodic reversal of energy flow.

QPM addresses this by flipping the sign of the nonlinear coefficient d_{eff} at regular intervals. In the most efficient case—first-order QPM—this reversal occurs every half coherence length, i.e., when the phase difference reaches π . At this point, the reversal of d resets the phase mismatch effectively to zero, allowing constructive interference to resume and accumulate over the full interaction length.

The *QPM order* refers to how many coherence lengths are spanned by one full period of nonlinear modulation. For first-order QPM, the poling period matches the coherence length: $\Lambda = l_c$. In higher-order QPM, the modulation is spaced more widely. For instance, in third-order QPM, the reversal occurs every 1.5 coherence lengths ($\Lambda = 3l_c$), and in fifth-order, every 2.5 coherence lengths ($\Lambda = 5l_c$). Since the SHG contribution still averages out to nearly zero over each full coherence length, higher-order QPM schemes are less efficient because only the final half coherence-length interval contributes positively before the next reset. Thus, the effective nonlinear coefficient decreases with increasing order.

Mathematically, the QPM condition is given by:

$$\Delta k = k_{2\omega} - 2k_\omega = \frac{2\pi m}{\Lambda}, \quad (2.22)$$

where m is the QPM order (an odd integer) and $\frac{2\pi m}{\Lambda}$ is the grating wavevector that compensates the phase mismatch.

Since the effective nonlinear coefficient scales inversely with the QPM order, the second-harmonic power decreases with increasing m . This trade-off is visually demonstrated in Fig. 2.4.

For BMF crystals, the domain size (half of the poling period) required for first-order quasi-phase matching (QPM) for second-harmonic generation (SHG) at 148.3 nm is calculated to be 0.4191 μm , assuming a type I interaction in the bbc configuration utilizing the highest nonlinear coefficient d_{32} . This calculation is based on Sellmeier coefficient data

Figure 2.4: Comparison of second-harmonic generation (SHG) amplitude between first-order and third-order periodic poling structures. The SHG signal generated using third-order poling is one third in amplitude than that from first-order poling, consistent with the reduced effective nonlinear coefficient associated with higher-order quasi-phase matching.

and nonlinear coefficients reported in [Villora 09]. The derivation and assumptions used in these calculations are detailed in Appendix A, including the domain width for other configurations. This sub-micron domain size is extremely challenging to fabricate with current poling techniques. Third-order QPM, which relaxes the poling constraints by tripling the period, increases the domain size to $1.2574\ \mu\text{m}$, making fabrication comparatively more feasible. However, even achieving these larger periods remains technologically demanding. Various methods, such as electron beam poling and double-needle approaches, are being explored to meet this challenge.

An alternative approach under investigation is *order-disorder* poling, also known as Additional Periodic Phase (APP) matching, which was initially proposed and demonstrated quartz and lithium niobate crystals [Shao 20]. In this method the crystal is structured with alternating ordered (crystalline) and disordered (amorphous) regions, thereby introducing an *additional phase difference* $\Delta\phi_{\text{APP}}$.

As discussed previously, when the phase mismatch parameter Δk is nonzero, the generated SHG wave accumulates a phase difference $\Delta\phi = \Delta k z$ with respect to the driving fundamental wave. When this phase difference reaches π , energy begins to flow back from

the second-harmonic to the fundamental wave, suppressing conversion efficiency. The key idea behind APP matching is to periodically reset this accumulated phase by introducing disordered regions that cause a phase jump of $\pm\pi$, thereby maintaining constructive interference over longer propagation distances.

This condition can be expressed as:

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{PD}} + \Delta\phi_{\text{APP}} = 2m\pi, 0 \quad (2.23)$$

where $\Delta\phi_{\text{PD}} = \Delta kz$ is the phase accumulated due to propagation, $\Delta\phi_{\text{APP}}$ is the additional phase jump introduced by the disordered region, and m is an integer. By carefully choosing the positions of the disordered segments, the phase mismatch can be compensated periodically, similar to QPM but without relying on ferroelectric domain inversion.

In practice, this is achieved by femtosecond laser writing, which locally destroys the nonlinear response of the crystal while slightly altering its refractive index. The grating structure has a period $\Lambda = L_a + L_b$, where L_a and L_b are the widths of the ordered and disordered segments, respectively. L_a and L_b should ideally be equal, and equal to domain width as calculated in the case of quasi phase matching, unless there is a significant difference in dispersion between the ordered and disordered regions.

Figure 2.5: Comparison of second-harmonic generation (SHG) amplitudes under different phase matching conditions: phase-matched, phase-mismatched, quasi-phase matched (QPM), and Additional Periodic Phase matched (APP). Phase matching yields maximum SHG due to perfect phase alignment. Phase mismatch leads to oscillating SHG amplitude from periodic dephasing. QPM restores constructive interference via periodic domain inversion. APP uses periodic disordered phases to achieve phase matching, resulting in lower SHG amplitude due to reduced effective nonlinearity. Adapted from [Shao 20].

Figure 2.5 compares the amplitude growth of the SHG signal for different phase-matching

schemes: perfect phase matching, quasi-phase matching, phase mismatch, and APP matching.

In this work, we present preliminary efforts to implement order-disorder poling in BMF crystals as a potential pathway to achieving phase matching for VUV generation. These initial results are promising but still require significant refinement and optimization.

2.4 Preliminary tests and Next Steps

To investigate the feasibility of order-disorder poling in BMF, preliminary tests were performed using a lithography laser system from LightFab GmbH (Aachen, Germany), located in the research group led by Prof. Ferdinand Schmidt-Kaler at the University of Mainz. The BMF crystal used in this study was grown by Mega Materials using high-purity BaF₂ and MgF₂ powders. The sample had dimensions of 5 mm (a-axis) × 10 mm (b-axis) × 1 mm (c-axis), with optical polishing on the 5 mm × 10 mm facets.

2.4.1 Laser Parameters

The lithography laser used for order-disorder poling has a wavelength of 1030 nm, a pulse width of 350 fs, a repetition rate of 200 kHz, and a focal spot size of approximately 2 × 15–25 μm, with a scan speed of 1 mm/s. In previous work on order-disorder poling in quartz crystals, the pulse energy was set to 8 μJ [Shao 20]. Since the optimal pulse energy for BMF crystals was not known, we adopted similar experimental conditions while scanning the pulse energy from 0 to 1800 nJ to determine the optimal parameters.

2.4.2 Experimental Procedure

The preliminary experiments involved varying the pulse energy from 0 to 1800 nJ. For each pulse energy value, 10 lines of 50 μm length were inscribed with a spacing of 10 μm. The modifications were introduced at a depth of 100 μm.

2.4.3 Results

The resulting modified crystal was imaged using a Leica AF7000 transmission microscope with crossed polarizers at the Institute of Molecular Biology (IMB), JGU Mainz. Due to the differing degrees of anisotropy between ordered and disordered regions, the modified regions appeared as regions with varied light transmission. Figure 2.6 shows the resulting transmission microscope image of the modified crystal.

Figure 2.6: Transmission microscope image of the modified crystal after order–disorder poling. The image shows 140 lines, with each set of 10 consecutive lines corresponding to a specific pulse energy. Starting from the left, the pulse energy decreases in steps of 200 nJ, from 1800 nJ to 1000 nJ, and then in steps of 100 nJ from 900 nJ down to 100 nJ. As the pulse energy decreases, the contrast in anisotropy of ordered and disordered regions diminishes, causing the lines to appear progressively fainter, with the 100 nJ lines being barely visible.

To quantitatively analyze the results, contrast as a function of pulse energy and the width of the modified region as a function of pulse energy were evaluated. Figure 2.7 shows these relationships.

(a) Contrast between modified and unmodified as a function of pulse energy.

(b) Width of modified region as a function of pulse energy.

Figure 2.7: Contrast and width of the laser-modified region as functions of pulse energy. A stable contrast plateau is observed between 400 and 1000 nJ/pulse, with a significant drop occurring beyond 1200 nJ/pulse due to material damage. The optimal pulse energy is identified at 400 nJ/pulse, providing both high contrast and minimal modification width, making it a strong candidate for further order–disorder structuring.

The contrast measurements as a function of pulse energy exhibit a plateau between 400 and 1000 nJ/pulse, indicating that the contrast remains stable over this range. However, a noticeable drop in contrast occurs as damage sets in around 1200 nJ/pulse. Among the tested pulse energies, the optimal conditions are achieved at 400 nJ/pulse, which provides both the best contrast and the smallest modification size. This suggests that 400 nJ/pulse is a promising candidate for further investigations.

To refine the optimization process, it is recommended to perform a more detailed energy

scan within a narrower range, specifically from 350 nJ to 450 nJ, using smaller step sizes. Once the optimal energy is confirmed and the modifications are reproducible, it will be possible to proceed with third-order poling in BMF crystals. Following this, additional parameters, such as the scan speed, can be varied and optimized to achieve the desired poling periods.

Furthermore, transmission measurements of the fundamental and second harmonic light through the disordered regions will be essential to verify their transparency. This will ensure that the disordered regions do not introduce excessive losses, which could hinder the overall SHG efficiency.

In conclusion, the preliminary results presented in this chapter demonstrate the feasibility of achieving order-disorder poling in BMF crystals. The identification of 400 nJ/pulse as a potential sweet spot for pulse energy is a promising development. Future efforts will focus on confirming the reproducibility of this result, performing fundamental transmission measurements, and exploring further optimization of lithography parameters to achieve poling of the BMF crystal.

Chapter 3

Cavity Locking for SHG Enhancement

3.1 Introduction

An optical resonator, or resonant optical cavity, is an arrangement of optical components that enables light to circulate in a closed path. Depending on their intended application, these resonators can take various forms, such as linear resonators or ring resonators. Linear resonators, also known as standing wave resonators, consist of two mirrors facing each other, allowing light to oscillate back and forth along a single axis. These cavities are commonly used in laser systems and precision spectroscopy due to their simple alignment and high stability. Ring resonators, on the other hand, are cavities where light propagates in a unidirectional path, typically through waveguides or free-space optics. Optical cavities are widely employed in laser systems, precision spectroscopy, quantum optics, and nonlinear optics due to their ability to confine light and significantly enhance its intracavity power through multiple reflections.

An enhancement cavity is a type of optical resonator designed to amplify optical power through resonance. When the incoming light is both resonant with the cavity and mode-matched, the circulating power within the cavity can become significantly greater than the input power, especially in high-finesse configurations. This principle is commonly leveraged for increasing the efficiency of the nonlinear processes where the efficiencies are low otherwise and where increased optical intensity enhances conversion efficiency.

Enhancement cavities are particularly valuable for second-harmonic generation (SHG). The efficiency of SHG is directly proportional to the power of the fundamental light beam [New 11], hence, placing a nonlinear crystal inside a resonant enhancement cavity allows for a significant increase in conversion efficiency. Even if only a small fraction of the circulating optical power is converted per round trip, the resonator effectively recycles unused light, leading to efficient frequency conversion. This approach is especially useful for generating coherent radiation at wavelengths that are otherwise difficult to access, such as in the

vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) spectral region. Figure 3.1 illustrates a specific type of enhancement cavity known as a bow-tie cavity, named for its distinctive geometric arrangement resembling a bow tie. This configuration consists of four mirrors that guide the circulating beam along a folded path, forming two crossing sections. Bow-tie cavities are commonly used for second-harmonic generation as they prevent the formation of standing waves of the fundamental wave inside the cavity. This is particularly advantageous because standing waves can induce photorefractive effects in the nonlinear crystal, which may degrade conversion efficiency and overall system performance. [Hannig 18]

Figure 3.1: The fundamental light is incoupled through mirror 1 inside the cavity and second harmonic is out coupled through mirror 4. The piezoelectric actuator is used to change the length of the cavity for its active stabilization, Adapted from [Hannig 18].

There are two main types of resonant frequency doubling: singly and doubly resonant frequency doubling. The singly resonant method involves making only the pump wave resonant while allowing the second-harmonic wave to exit the cavity. The enhanced circulating power of the pump wave improves conversion efficiency. Although the single pass conversion efficiency may be really less, this can suffice to achieve high overall efficiency due to the power build-up within the cavity.

In the doubly resonant method, both the pump wave and the second harmonic wave are resonant inside the cavity. The highest conversion efficiencies can be achieved by this method for very low pump powers [Fiedler 93]. It requires precise control over two independent parameters—typically the nonlinear crystal’s temperature and the cavity length—to ensure stable operation. For more detailed theoretical description see following reference [Boyd 68].

In our case, for a Barium Magnesium Fluoride (BMF) crystal, we calculated the single-pass SHG efficiency using the Boyd-Kleinman formalism [Boyd 68], (see Appendix B). For the available crystal length and focusing parameters, the expected single-pass efficiency is $1.76 \times 10^{-5} \%$. With cavity enhancement, this efficiency can be increased without requiring extreme pump powers.

This chapter focuses on optical cavities and the techniques used to stabilize them for precise operation. Section 3.2 provides the theoretical framework of optical cavities, covering resonance conditions, transmission and reflection properties, and the impact of cavity length fluctuations. By analyzing how small variations in cavity length disrupt resonance, this section highlights the necessity of active stabilization. Section 3.3 introduces the Hänsch-Couillaud locking technique and its two variations, explaining their working principles and how they help maintain cavity resonance. Section 3.4 presents the experimental setup used in this work, detailing the implementation of the cavity locking system and evaluating its performance through measurements such as the incoupling efficiencies and power enhancement factor.

3.2 Theory of Optical Cavities

Optical cavities function based on the principle of multiple-beam interference, where light undergoes multiple reflections between highly reflective mirrors. These reflections result in constructive or destructive interference depending on the phase accumulated during each round trip. To understand multiple-beam interference, we follow the standard approach [Born 19] by first analyzing interference in a plane-parallel plate. Figure 3.2 shows a plane-parallel plate with a refractive index n' placed in a medium with refractive index n . When light from a monochromatic source P strikes the plate at point A_1 , part of the beam is reflected in the direction A_1C_1 while the remaining portion is transmitted, following the path A_1B_1 . At B_1 , the beam is again partially reflected along B_1A_2 and partially transmitted along B_1D_1 . This division of the wave continues within the plate, creating a series of reflected and transmitted beams, as shown in the figure 2.

Let $A^{(i)}$ be the initial complex amplitude of the beam. Also as we know from Fresnel's equations that transmission and reflection coefficients depends on the polarization of the incident wave, hence to keep things simple we assume the light to either be s or p polarized. The phase difference between successive reflected and transmitted beams corresponds to a double pass through the plate and is given by:

$$\delta = \frac{4\pi n' d \cos \theta'}{\lambda_0}, \quad (3.1)$$

where λ_0 is the wavelength of the light in the vacuum. We define the reflection and transmission coefficients for a wave incident on a plate as follows:

- r_1 and t_1 are the reflection and transmission coefficients for a wave traveling from the surrounding medium to the plate.
- r_2 and t_2 are the reflection and transmission coefficients for a wave traveling from the plate to the surrounding medium.

Figure 3.2: Multiple reflections in a plane-parallel plate, illustrating the principle of multiple-beam interference. A monochromatic beam undergoes successive partial reflections and transmissions within the plate, leading to a series of interfering beams. This setup serves as a foundational model for understanding the behavior of optical cavities, where constructive and destructive interference arise from phase accumulation over multiple round trips.

Using the Fresnel equations, it can be shown that for either polarization[Born 19], the reflection and transmission coefficients satisfy the following relations:

$$t_1 t_2 = T, \quad (3.2)$$

where T is the transmissivity at any of the two boundaries. Furthermore, the reflection coefficients are related by:

$$r_1 = -r_2 \quad \text{and} \quad r_1^2 = r_2^2 = R, \quad (3.3)$$

where R is the reflectivity at any of the two boundaries.

The complex amplitudes of the reflected waves form a geometric series:

$$A_{\text{ref}} = r_1 A^{(i)} + t_1 t_2 r_2 e^{i\delta} A^{(i)} + t_1 t_2 r_2^3 e^{i2\delta} A^{(i)} + \dots \quad (3.4)$$

Summing this infinite geometric series, the total reflected amplitude becomes:

$$A_{\text{ref}} = -\frac{r_2(1 - (r_2^2 + t_1 t_2)e^{i\delta})}{1 - r_2^2 e^{i\delta}} A^{(i)}. \quad (3.5)$$

Substituting from equations (3.2) and (3.3), and calculating the intensity as the square of the amplitude, the reflected intensity is given by:

$$I_{\text{ref}} = \frac{4R \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}}{(1-R)^2 + 4R \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}} I^{(i)}, \quad (3.6)$$

Similarly the complex amplitudes of the transmitted waves also form a geometric series:

$$A_{\text{trans}} = t_1 t_2 A^{(i)} + t_1 t_2 r_1^2 e^{i\delta} A^{(i)} + t_1 t_2 r_1^4 e^{i2\delta} A^{(i)} + \dots \quad (3.7)$$

Summing the series, the total transmitted amplitude becomes:

$$A_{\text{trans}} = \frac{t_1 t_2}{1 - r_1^2 e^{i\delta}} A^{(i)}. \quad (3.8)$$

So, the transmitted intensity is:

$$I_{\text{trans}} = \frac{T^2}{(1-R)^2 + 4R \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}} I^{(i)}, \quad (3.9)$$

Now, if the parameter F is defined as

$$F = \frac{4R}{(1-R)^2} \quad (3.10)$$

and using the relation $R + T = 1$, the expressions for the reflected and transmitted intensities (normalized to the incident intensity) modify to:

$$I^{(r)} = \frac{F \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}}{1 + F \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}}, \quad (3.11)$$

$$I^{(t)} = \frac{1}{1 + F \sin^2 \frac{\delta}{2}}. \quad (3.12)$$

Figure 3.3(a) shows the plot of $I^{(r)}$ and $I^{(t)}$. It is evident that when the transmitted intensity is at its maximum, the reflected intensity is at its minimum, which is intuitive. This behavior arises because maximum transmission corresponds to minimal reflection due to energy conservation in the system.

Figure 3.4 shows the transmitted intensity for different values of the parameter F . As the value of F increases, the sharpness of the resonance (i.e., the peak where the transmitted intensity is maximized) increases. This behavior is also intuitive because higher reflectivity increases the number of interfering waves within the cavity. A larger number of interfering waves results in sharper fringes due to enhanced constructive and destructive interference.

A useful parameter for quantifying the sharpness of resonance is the finesse \mathcal{F} , defined as the ratio of the free spectral range (the spacing between adjacent resonances) to the half-width of the resonance peak. It can be shown that the finesse is related to the parameter F by:

$$\mathcal{F} = \frac{\pi\sqrt{F}}{2}. \quad (3.13)$$

Figure 3.3: (a) Reflected and transmitted intensities as functions of the phase shift δ , illustrating the resonance condition in an optical cavity where interference effects lead to sharp modulation of intensity. (b) Reflected and transmitted intensities as functions of the cavity length h , emphasizing the sensitivity of the cavity response to length variations. Even nanometer-scale changes in cavity length lead to significant shifts in intensity, demonstrating the need for precise stabilization to maintain resonance.

Figure 3.4: Normalized transmitted intensity as a function of phase shift for different finesse values. Higher finesse results in sharper resonance peaks due to lower cavity losses, while lower finesse leads to broader, less selective transmission profiles.

Additionally, if the contrast factor of the transmitted signal is defined as the ratio of maximum to minimum transmitted intensity:

$$C = \frac{I_{\max}^{(t)}}{I_{\min}^{(t)}}, \quad (3.14)$$

Then the finesse is related to the contrast factor by:

$$C = 1 + F = 1 + \frac{4\mathcal{F}^2}{\pi^2}. \quad (3.15)$$

Two important parameter used to characterize an enhancement cavity are *power enhancement factor* \mathcal{E} and incoupling efficiency. Power enhancement factor \mathcal{E} is defined as the ratio of the steady-state intracavity power P_{cav} to the input power P_{in} :

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{P_{\text{cav}}}{P_{\text{in}}}. \quad (3.16)$$

The finesse \mathcal{F} and the power enhancement factor \mathcal{E} for a bow tie cavity are related by [Patimisco 17]:

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{\mathcal{F}}{2\pi}. \quad (3.17)$$

The incoupling efficiency of an optical cavity quantifies how effectively the input laser power is coupled into the cavity. It is defined as the fraction of input power that enters the cavity rather than being reflected:

$$\eta_{\text{incoupling}} = \frac{P_{\text{in}} - P_{\text{reflected}}}{P_{\text{in}}}, \quad (3.18)$$

where P_{in} is the incident laser power and $P_{\text{reflected}}$ is the power reflected from the cavity. High incoupling efficiency indicates good mode matching and cavity alignment.

Figure 3.3(b) shows the plot of a single resonance as a function of the cavity length h . This plot is calculated for a wavelength of 500 nm at normal incidence. The sharpness of the resonance, characterized by the high finesse of the cavity, implies that even a small variation in cavity length of just a few nanometers is sufficient to shift the system out of resonance. This sensitivity arises because the optical path length within the cavity must satisfy strict resonance conditions, which are easily perturbed by mechanical vibrations, thermal expansion, and even acoustic disturbances caused by sound waves.

Maintaining resonance under such stringent conditions necessitates active stabilization of the cavity length using a feedback loop. Without such stabilization, the cavity would quickly drift out of resonance, leading to a loss of circulating power and reduced efficiency in processes like second-harmonic generation (SHG). The next section discusses a widely used cavity locking method known as the Hänsch-Couillaud technique, along with its two variations.

3.3 Cavity stabilization methods

Maintaining optical resonance in a high-finesse cavity requires active stabilization of the cavity length. Even small fluctuations in the cavity length, on the order of a few nanometers,

can shift the cavity out of resonance and reduce circulating power. To counteract this, a feedback loop is typically employed to actively control the cavity length and maintain resonance.

A feedback loop operates by generating an error signal that reflects the deviation of the cavity length from the optimal resonance condition. This error signal is derived from the reflected or transmitted light from the cavity, and it provides real-time information about the phase or frequency mismatch. The error signal is processed by a feedback controller, which adjusts the length of the cavity, often using a piezoelectric actuator mounted on one of the cavity mirrors, to minimize the error and restore resonance.

The generated error signal is typically dispersion-shaped antisymmetric, S-shaped signal that resembles the derivative of a Lorentzian. This shape arises because the phase response of the cavity changes rapidly near resonance, similar to the dispersive behavior of a medium near an absorption line. The zero-crossing point of the signal corresponds to the resonance condition, making it ideal for feedback stabilization. The slope of the error signal near the zero-crossing determines the sensitivity of the locking technique.

Various methods have been developed to generate a suitable error signal and implement cavity locking [Honda 09][Drever 83][Helmcke 82]. In this section, one such technique, the Hänsch-Couillaud locking method, will be briefly explained; a more detailed description can be found in the original paper by Hänsch and Couillaud. [Hänsch 80]

To understand the Hänsch-Couillaud locking technique, it is helpful to first examine the experimental setup, as shown in Fig. 3.5. The setup consists of three main components: a laser, an optical cavity, and an analyzer. A linearly polarized beam with an initial amplitude $E^{(i)}$ from the laser is coupled into the cavity.

The coupling can be done in two different ways:

- **On-axis coupling:** The incident beam is aligned with the optical axis of the cavity. In this case, a beam splitter is used to direct the reflected beam toward the analyzer as shown in the figure.
- **Off-axis coupling:** The incident and reflected beams make a small angle with each other, and the analyzer is positioned along the reflected beam's path. This off-axis arrangement was proposed in the original Hänsch-Couillaud paper.

The coordinate system is defined such that the cavity contains a linear polarizer with its transmission axis aligned along the a -axis. The incoming beam is polarized at an angle θ relative to this transmission axis. This incident beam can be decomposed into two orthogonal components: one along the transmission axis and the other perpendicular to it. The amplitudes of these two components are:

Figure 3.5: Schematic of the Hänsch-Couillaud locking setup. The input beam is polarized at an angle to the cavity axis defined by a linear polarizer. The cavity reflects the perpendicular polarization while resonating the parallel component. The reflected beam passes through a quarter-wave plate (QWP) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), which converts polarization differences into an intensity imbalance used to generate an error signal similar to schematic provided in [Bir 97].

$$E_a^{(i)} = E^{(i)} \cos \theta \quad (3.19)$$

$$E_b^{(i)} = E^{(i)} \sin \theta \quad (3.20)$$

where $E_a^{(i)}$ and $E_b^{(i)}$ are the amplitudes of the electric field components parallel and perpendicular to the transmission axis, respectively. The component that is perpendicular to the transmission axis cannot resonate inside the cavity. Hence, the reflected component of this part is simply:

$$E_b^{(r)} = E_b^{(i)} \sqrt{R_1} \quad (3.21)$$

where R_1 is the reflectivity of the entrance mirror M_1 .

The parallel component, on the other hand, can resonate within the cavity and pick up a phase shift depending on the cavity length. Following a similar procedure as described in Section 3.2, the reflected parallel component is given by:

$$E_a^{(r)} = E_{\parallel}^{(i)} \left(\sqrt{R_1} - \frac{T_1 R}{\sqrt{R_1} (1 - R)^2 + 4R \sin^2 \frac{1}{2} \delta} \right) \quad (3.22)$$

where R_1 and T_1 are the reflectivity and transmissivity of the entrance mirror, and R is the amplitude ratio of the electric field from successive round trips, which accounts for all other losses including the loss due to the linear polarizer inside the cavity.

The reflected light is then passed through an analyzer consisting of a quarter-wave plate (QWP) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS). The fast axis of the QWP is aligned along the cavity transmission axis a , and output P of the PBS is oriented at an angle of 45° with respect to the fast axis of the QWP.

At exact resonance ($\delta = 2m\pi$), both the parallel and perpendicular components remain in phase, and the reflected beam is linearly polarized. Off-resonance, however, the parallel component acquires an additional phase due to the imaginary part of $E_a^{(r)}$, causing the reflected beam to become elliptically polarized.

To detect this ellipticity, which contains information about the phase shift acquired within the cavity, the reflected light is passed through the analyzer. The Jones matrix representation of the QWP with its fast axis along the a -axis is:

$$J_{\text{QWP}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.23)$$

The Jones matrix for the PBS, which acts as a rotation matrix at an angle of 45° , is:

$$J_{\text{PBS}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.24)$$

Acting these matrices on the column vector of the reflected components:

$$\begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} E_a^{(r)} \\ iE_b^{(r)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

The intensities I_1 and I_2 are directly proportional to $|E_1|^2$ and $|E_2|^2$ respectively. Using this relation along with equations (3.16), (3.17), (3.18), (3.19), and (3.22), we obtain the difference signal:

$$I_a - I_b = I^{(i)} 2 \cos \theta \sin \theta \frac{T_1 R \sin \delta}{(1 - R)^2 + 4R \sin^2 \frac{1}{2} \delta} \quad (3.26)$$

This function was analyzed by Hänsch and Couillaud, who demonstrated that it produces a dispersive error signal. This error signal can be used to adjust the cavity length, enabling active stabilization to the resonance condition.

A variation of this method, in which a birefringent material inside the cavity is used instead of a linear polarizer to generate the error signal, was proposed in 1997[Bir 97]. Figure 3.6 shows a schematic diagram in which the linear polarizer is replaced with a uniaxial birefringent material whose optic axis lies in the ac plane. Since the light is traveling along the

c -direction, it can be polarized along the a - and b -directions. As the optic axis is in the ac plane, the component of the electric field along the a -direction is called the extraordinary wave, and the refractive index (n_e) experienced by this wave depends on the orientation of the optic axis in the ac plane. On the other hand, the wave along the b -direction experiences a constant refractive index (n_o) and is called the ordinary wave.

Figure 3.6: Schematic of the cavity stabilization technique using a birefringent material placed inside the cavity to generate an error signal. Due to birefringent crystal inside the cavity a phase shift is introduced between the ordinary and extraordinary components of the circulating light. An analyzer assembly, consisting of a quarter-wave plate (QWP) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), converts this polarization change into an intensity difference between two orthogonal polarization components, which is then used to generate an error signal for locking. The schematic is adapted from [Bir 97].

Similar to the Hänsch-Couillaud scheme, the cavity is illuminated with light polarized at an angle θ with respect to the a -axis. In this case, both the a - and b -components can resonate inside the cavity. Consequently, the reflected light from the cavity has three components:

- Light reflected directly by the entrance mirror M_1 .
- Light resonating in the a -direction.
- Light resonating in the b -direction.

Due to the different refractive indices of the crystal, the latter two components acquire different phases, δ_a and δ_b , inside the cavity. The reflected beam is then represented by:

$$E_{a,b}^{(r)} = E_{a,b}^{(i)} \left(\sqrt{R_1} - \frac{T_1 R \cos \delta_{a,b} - R + i \sin \delta_{a,b}}{\sqrt{R_1} (1 - R)^2 + 4R \sin^2 \frac{\delta_{a,b}}{2}} \right) \quad (3.27)$$

Here, R_1 and T_1 are the reflectivity and transmissivity of the entrance mirror M_1 , respectively, while R is the amplitude ratio representing the total round-trip loss in the cavity similar to Hänsch-Couillaud technique.

The reflected beam is analyzed using a similar setup as in the Hänsch-Couillaud scheme, consisting of a quarter-wave plate (QWP) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS). The PBS is oriented such that its output P is at 45 degrees to the fast axis of the QWP. The two output beams are measured using two photodiodes, and the resulting signals are subtracted to obtain an error signal. This error signal exhibits two sharp edges: one corresponding to the ordinary wave and the other to the extraordinary wave. The cavity can be locked to either the extraordinary or the ordinary component of the light, depending on the desired resonance condition. Figure 3.7 shows the error signal as a function of phase difference of ordinary waves as reported in the original paper. For a more detailed description and analysis of the error signal, refer to the original publication [Bir 97].

Figure 3.7: Error signal in case of birefringent material inside the cavity (a) For low loss cavity (b) For high loss cavity.

Many dielectric mirrors exhibit weak birefringence[Berceau 10], which can introduce polarization dependent phase shifts and affect cavity stability. In 2011, a cavity stabilization method that exploits this intrinsic birefringence[Asenbaum 11] was proposed. In this approach the entire cavity is treated as a single effective birefringent element, allowing the birefringence to generate an error signal for active cavity stabilization. We employ this method to lock our enhancement cavity used for 2nd harmonic generation at 148.3nm. The

next section details the experimental setup and presents the error signal and cavity transmission signals before and after locking.

3.4 Setup and Results

A Continuous-Wave (cw) laser at 148.3 nm can be generated using second-harmonic generation (SHG) from a laser at double the wavelength. The fundamental beam at 296.75 nm was provided by a frequency-quadrupled high-power diode laser system (**DLC DL-FA-FHG PRO**, Topica Photonics). Figure 3.8 shows a schematic of this laser system, where a seed laser at 1187 nm is frequency doubled in two stages to produce the final output at 296.75 nm. As discussed in the previous sections, coupling the fundamental source into an enhancement cavity is essential for increasing the efficiency of second-harmonic generation. Figure 3.9 shows a schematic of the experimental setup used to couple the fundamental source at 296.75 nm into a bow-tie enhancement cavity, along with the opto-electronic system employed to lock the cavity on resonance. The actual experimental setup is shown in Fig. 3.10, which includes photographs of the surrounding optics and the bow-tie cavity with labeled components.

Figure 3.8: Commercial **DLC DL-FA-FHG PRO** Topica laser system operating at 296.75 nm, used as the fundamental source for second-harmonic generation (SHG) to produce 148.3 nm light. The system consists of a seed laser at 1187 nm, which undergoes two successive stages of frequency doubling—first to 593.5 nm and then to 296.75 nm. This UV output is then coupled into a bow-tie cavity for further frequency conversion into the vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) region.

For vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) generation, additional challenges arise due to the strong absorption of VUV light in air and most optical materials. As a result, the bow-tie cavity—where second-harmonic generation (SHG) occurs—must be placed entirely inside a vacuum chamber to ensure efficient propagation of the generated 148.3 nm light. This imposes strict constraints on the alignment, mechanical stability, and choice of materials used in the cavity design.

The light from the pump cw laser is passed through a half-wave plate(HW1) to adjust the plane of polarization as required. It then passes through a polarization beam splitter(PBS),

which is used to clean the polarization by separating the two orthogonal polarization components. The unwanted polarization is directed to a beam dump (BD). Mirrors MW1 and MW2 are used to steer the laser beam for coupling into the cavity.

Figure 3.9: Experimental setup of the bow-tie enhancement cavity and surrounding optics. The fundamental beam from the cw laser is polarization-cleaned using a half-wave plate (HW1) and a polarizing beam splitter (PBS), then mode-matched to the cavity using lenses L1 and L2 on translation stages. Mirrors MW1 and MW2 steer the beam into the cavity formed by four mirrors (M1–M4), with M1 as the incoupling mirror and M2 mounted on a piezo actuator for cavity length control. Reflected light is analyzed via a Hänsch-Couillaud locking scheme using a quarter-wave plate, PBS, and photodiodes P1 and P2. The resulting error signal is processed by a PID controller to maintain resonance.

Before coupling, the beam is passed through two lenses, L1 and L2, with focal lengths of +150 mm and +100 mm, respectively. These lenses are used for spatial mode matching, ensuring that the spatial mode of the pump light beam overlaps with the circulating mode inside the cavity. The distances of the lenses from the cavity waist were calculated using the method described in[Francois 71]. For fine adjustment, the lenses are mounted on z-translation stages to precisely tune their distances from the cavity waist. Additionally, the lenses are mounted on 6-axis kinematic mounts from Thorlabs, providing angular tuning freedom for optimal alignment.

The bow-tie cavity is formed by four mirrors: M1, M2, M3, and M4. This cavity was custom-designed by Agile Optic for efficient second-harmonic generation at 148.3 nm using a BMF crystal. Mirror M1 serves as the incoupling mirror, while mirror M2 is mounted on a piezoelectric actuator with a range of motion sufficient to adjust the cavity length by more than one free spectral range. Both mirrors M3 and M4 can be used to monitor the transmitted light. A power meter (PM) is mounted behind M4 to measure the

(a) Photograph of the surrounding optics. The lenses L1 and L2, as well as the steering mirrors MW1 and MW2, are marked.

(b) Photograph of the bow-tie enhancement cavity showing the four mirrors (M1–M4) that form the resonator.

Figure 3.10: Photographs of the actual experimental setup. (a) Surrounding optics for beam preparation and coupling. (b) Bow-tie enhancement cavity used for SHG.

transmitted power.

The light reflected from M1 is directed toward the analyzer assembly, which follows the Hänsch-Couillaud locking scheme. The analyzer consists of a quarter-wave plate (λ) and a PBS. The two polarization components are focused on two photodiodes P1 and P2 using L3 and L4 respectively. The difference signal from the photodiodes generates the error signal, which is processed using a PID controller—also designed by Agile Optic—and fed into the piezoelectric actuator to lock the cavity to resonance.

The error signal generated from the Hänsch-Couillaud locking scheme was used to lock the cavity to resonance. Figure 3.11 presents the measured cavity signals. Figure 3.11(a) shows the error signal and the transmitted signal measured behind mirror M4 as the piezo actuator is scanned. Figure 3.11(b) shows the reflected and transmitted signals after the cavity has been locked. The constant transmitted power in Figure 3.11(b) confirms that the cavity is successfully locked at resonance.

Figure 3.12 presents the measurements used to calculate the incoupling efficiency. To determine the efficiency, one of the photodiodes was blocked to measure the signal drop at resonance. Similarly, the other photodiode was blocked to measure the corresponding drop. The incoupling efficiency is determined by calculating the percentage drop in reflected power at cavity resonance. Ideally, the incoupling efficiencies calculated from both signals should be identical. However, if the cavity is not properly aligned, the two values may differ, indicating the need for further optimization. Figure 3.12(a) shows the signal from the positive photodiode, and Figure 3.12(b) shows the signal from the negative photodiode.

Figure 3.11: Error and cavity signals during piezo scan and active locking. (a) Error signal and transmitted signal measured behind mirror M4 while the cavity length is scanned using a piezo actuator. Varying the cavity length causes the resonance condition to periodically align with the fixed laser frequency, producing a dispersive-shaped error signal and transmission peaks. (b) Reflected and transmitted signals after locking the cavity. The feedback loop continuously adjusts the cavity length via the piezo to maintain resonance, resulting in stable transmitted power indicating successful cavity locking.

The incoupling efficiency calculated from the positive photodiode signal was 76.05%, while the value from the negative photodiode signal was 87.20%, resulting in an average incoupling efficiency of 81.62%.

Figure 3.12: Photodiode signals used to calculate the incoupling efficiency of the cavity. The incoupling efficiency is determined by calculating the percentage drop in reflected power at cavity resonance. The calculated efficiencies are 76.05% and 87.20% from positive photodiode and negative photodiode measurements respectively, resulting in an average incoupling efficiency of 81.62%. (a) Signal from the positive photodiode, measuring the drop in the reflected power at cavity resonance. (b) Signal from the negative photodiode, again measuring the drop in the reflected power at cavity resonance.

Figure 3.13: Cavity transmission and error signals during laser frequency scan. (a) Transmitted signal behind mirror M4 and corresponding error signal when the cavity is unlocked. As the pump laser frequency is slowly scanned, different frequencies accumulate different phase shifts within the cavity, resulting in a periodic transmission pattern corresponding to the cavity resonances. (b) Transmitted signal after locking the cavity. The feedback system continuously adjusts the cavity length in response to the error signal to maintain resonance, resulting in a stable transmitted power and demonstrating successful cavity locking.

Figure 3.13 demonstrates the stability of the cavity lock. Figure 3.13(a) shows the transmitted signal behind mirror M4 and the error signal when the pump laser frequency is slowly scanned with the cavity unlocked. In Figure 3.13(b), the cavity is first locked, and then the pump laser frequency is slowly scanned. The stable transmitted signal in Figure 3.13(b) confirms that the cavity remains locked, indicating the stability of the lock. To calculate the power enhancement factor, the transmitted power was measured by first blocking the light reflected from mirror M4 to mirror M1. Similarly, the transmitted power was measured after locking the cavity. Taking into account the measured incoupling efficiency of 81.62%, the power enhancement factor for the fundamental wave inside the cavity was calculated to be 19.95. Using the relation between the enhancement factor and the finesse introduced in Equation (3.17), the finesse of the cavity was calculated to be 125.3. Under ideal conditions, assuming no absorption or scattering losses in the SHG crystal, this enhancement factor would result in an enhancement of the second-harmonic power by approximately a factor of 400 compared to single-pass conversion. Based on the single-pass SHG power calculated using the Boyd-Kleinman formalism (see Appendix B), this corresponds to an ideal output power of approximately $20\mu\text{W}$ for 1st order quasi phase matching and nonlinear coefficient d_{32} . However, this represents an optimistic upper limit; in practice, the actual output power will be lower due to loss mechanisms such as absorption, scattering, and imperfect phase matching in the nonlinear crystal, whose contributions

will need to be quantitatively estimated. This demonstrates the effectiveness of the cavity locking scheme in achieving high circulating power, which is essential for efficient second harmonic generation. Table 3.1 summarizes the key cavity parameters and experimental results relevant to the SHG enhancement setup. Next chapter describes a detection system for Vacuum Ultraviolet laser light.

Table 3.1: Summary of cavity parameters and results

Parameter	Value
Incoupling efficiency	81.62 %
Power enhancement factor	19.95
Finesse	125.3
Mode-matching lenses (L1, L2)	+150 mm and +100 mm focal lengths
Single-pass SHG output power, P_{SHG}^{\dagger}	5.3×10^{-8} W
Estimated SHG power (ideal, no losses)	20 μ W
Incoupling waist ($1/e^2$ radius, horizontal)*	144 μ m
Incoupling waist ($1/e^2$ radius, vertical)*	164 μ m
Beam waist at crystal ($1/e^2$ radius, horizontal)*	44 μ m
Beam waist at crystal ($1/e^2$ radius, vertical)*	45 μ m
Experimental incoupling waist ($1/e^2$ radius, horizontal)	138.95 μ m
Experimental incoupling waist ($1/e^2$ radius, vertical)	156.75 μ m

*Values suggested by Agile Optic based on cavity design.

[†]see Appendix B.

Chapter 4

Detection System for VUV Light

4.1 Introduction

Detecting vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) light presents significant challenges due to the limited availability of efficient detectors and the presence of background radiation. In this work, a dedicated detection system was assembled to measure low powers of VUV light at 148.3 nm at the level of individual photons. In the eventuality that very low VUV light would be produced, a system capable of single-photon detection is desired.

To achieve this, a head-on type photomultiplier tube (PMT) with a CsI photocathode from Hamamatsu Photonics, [R1081](#), was used due to its high sensitivity and fast response time [[Zheng 20](#)]. Although the selected PMT is designed for the VUV spectral region (115–200 nm), it still exhibits a small but non-zero quantum efficiency at longer wavelengths, including the fundamental at 297 nm. The quantum efficiency at this wavelength is on the order of 10^{-8} , meaning that roughly one in every 10^8 incident photons can generate a detectable signal.

To estimate the background signal due to stray 297 nm light, consider a 300 mW beam. The energy of a single photon at this wavelength is approximately 6.6×10^{-19} J, corresponding to a photon flux of:

$$\Phi = \frac{P}{E_{\text{photon}}} = \frac{0.3 \text{ W}}{6.6 \times 10^{-19} \text{ J}} \approx 4.5 \times 10^{17} \text{ photons/s.}$$

Even if only a small fraction of this light—say, one part in a million—reaches the PMT due to scattering or diffuse reflections, the photon flux at the detector would still be on the order of 10^{11} photons/s. Applying the detector’s approximate quantum efficiency at 300 nm:

$$N_{\text{counts}} \approx 10^{11} \text{ photons/s} \times 10^{-8} = 10^3 \text{ photons/s.}$$

This shows that stray UV light from the fundamental beam can produce thousands of background counts per second, even with extremely low detection efficiency. This underscores the importance of implementing effective filtering strategies to suppress the fundamental wavelength when detecting weak VUV signals.

Since the system is designed to detect low photon flux, a single photon counter from Vertilon Corporation, [MCPC618](#), was used for data acquisition. This allows for precise measurement of individual photon detection events, enabling a quantitative analysis of the VUV signal.

This chapter describes the detection system in detail, beginning with the working principle of the PMT, followed by the implementation of background-reducing filters and photon counting, and concluding with an analysis of the system's performance.

4.2 Functionality of the Photomultiplier Tube (PMT)

This section is mainly based on [[Hamamatsu 17](#)] unless stated otherwise. A photomultiplier tube (PMT) is a highly sensitive detector capable of measuring extremely low light levels by converting incident photons into an amplified electrical signal. This amplification process makes PMTs particularly useful for applications requiring the detection of weak optical signals, such as vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) light generated using SHG.

The operation of a PMT relies on the photoelectric effect, wherein incident photons strike a photocathode, causing the emission of electrons via photoemission. These emitted electrons are then accelerated toward a series of dynodes, which are specially coated electrodes designed to facilitate electron multiplication. Each dynode is maintained at a progressively higher potential, and as an electron strikes a dynode, it releases multiple secondary electrons through impact ionization. This cascading amplification process continues across multiple dynode stages, leading to an exponential increase in the number of electrons. Finally, the multiplied electrons reach the anode, where they are collected and converted into an electrical signal proportional to the incident photon flux.

One of the key advantages of PMTs is their ability to achieve extremely high gain, often on the order of 10^6 to 10^7 , making them ideal for single-photon counting applications. Additionally, their fast response times allow for time-resolved measurements, which is again beneficial for detecting single photons.

4.2.1 Internal Structure of a PMT

A photomultiplier tube (PMT) consists of several key components as shown in Fig. [4.1](#), each playing a crucial role in the detection and amplification of photons. The main compo-

nents of a PMT are:

- **Photocathode** – The front surface of the PMT is coated with a photosensitive material that ejects electrons when struck by incident photons via the photoelectric effect. The efficiency of this process is characterized by the photocathode's quantum efficiency (QE), which determines the probability of an incident photon generating a photoelectron.
- **Electron Focusing System** – After photoemission, the ejected electrons are directed toward the first dynode using a focusing electrode. Proper focusing ensures efficient electron collection and minimizes signal loss.
- **Dynode Chain and Voltage Divider Circuit** – The core amplification stage consists of a series of dynodes, which are electrodes designed to facilitate electron multiplication through secondary emission. Each dynode is maintained at a progressively higher potential using a voltage divider circuit, which typically consists of a series of resistors connected across a high-voltage power supply. This circuit ensures a stable potential difference between consecutive dynodes, allowing electrons to be efficiently accelerated and multiplied at each stage. The total gain of the PMT depends on the number of dynode stages and the secondary electron emission ratio at each step.
- **Anode** – The final stage of the PMT, where the multiplied electrons are collected to produce a measurable electrical signal. The output signal is exponentially proportional to the number of incident photons, making PMTs highly sensitive to low-light conditions.

The overall performance of a PMT is determined by factors such as the choice of photocathode material, the number and design of dynode stages, and the applied high-voltage potential. These parameters influence the gain, response time, and spectral sensitivity of the detector.

4.2.2 Spectral Sensitivity & Choice of Photocathode

The spectral sensitivity of a photomultiplier tube (PMT) is primarily determined by the photocathode material, which dictates the range of wavelengths the PMT can effectively detect. Different photocathode materials exhibit varying quantum efficiencies (QE) across different spectral regions, from ultraviolet (UV) to near-infrared (NIR).

For VUV detection, alkali metal-based photocathodes are commonly used due to their high photoemission efficiency in the deep ultraviolet region such as tellurides Cs_2Te , Rb_2Te , Cs-K-Te , and Rb-K-Te [Zhang 17] or halides CsI , CsBr , KI are commonly used due to their

Figure 4.1: Schematic of a typical photomultiplier tube (PMT), with the voltage divider circuit omitted for clarity. The device consists of a photocathode, where incident photons generate photoelectrons via the photoelectric effect, followed by a series of dynodes that multiply the signal through secondary electron emission. The resulting amplified electron cascade is collected at the anode to produce a measurable current. Adapted from [Hamamatsu 17].

high quantum efficiency in the vacuum ultraviolet range. Out of these CsI is most widely used because of its high quantum efficiency[Breskin 96]. These materials have high photoemission yield but require a window material that is transmissive to VUV photons, such as magnesium fluoride (MgF_2) or fused silica.

Additionally, PMTs designed for VUV applications are often operated in vacuum-sealed or nitrogen-purged environments to prevent absorption of short-wavelength light by atmospheric oxygen. The selection of a suitable photocathode and window material is critical for optimizing the detection efficiency of VUV photons while minimizing background noise from unwanted wavelengths.

4.3 Performance and Results

In this work, we use the Hamamatsu R1081 photomultiplier tube (PMT), a solar-blind detector specifically designed for vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) detection in the wavelength range of 115 nm to 200 nm, with peak sensitivity around 140 nm. It features a 10-stage linear-focused dynode structure, providing high gain and efficient electron multiplication. The PMT is equipped with a Cs-I photocathode and an MgF_2 window, ensuring optimal detection efficiency for VUV photons while minimizing sensitivity to longer wavelengths. For our application, the PMT is operated at 2000 V, allowing it to function in single-photon counting mode, where it achieves a typical gain of 10^6 [Hamamatsu 17]. At higher photon flux, the PMT can also be operated in DC mode, where the output is a continuous current proportional to the incident photon flux.

Figure 4.2: Voltage divider circuit for a photomultiplier tube (PMT). It consists of a simple chain of resistors connected across a high-voltage supply, providing stepped voltages to each dynode stage. This ensures the correct potential difference needed for sequential electron multiplication. Adapted from [Hamamatsu 17].

To power the PMT, a voltage divider circuit was built, as shown in Fig.4.2. This circuit distributes the high voltage across the cathode, dynodes, and anode, ensuring proper electron multiplication at each dynode stage.

To convert the anode current into a measurable voltage signal, an external transimpedance amplifier (DHPCA-100) from femto was used with an amplification factor of 10^4 V/A. Figure 4.3a displays a typical single-photon pulse observed on an oscilloscope. The pulse width was measured to be approximately 50 ns, indicating that as long as individual photon events are separated by at least this time interval, they can be reliably counted as discrete photon detections.

When the PMT is operated at high voltage (2000 V) with a high external amplification factor of 10^4 V/A, a certain level of electronic noise is introduced. This noise, typically ranging between -30 mV and 30 mV, is shown in Fig.4.3b. In this figure, a single-photon pulse can also be observed, originating from ambient light present in the room. So, even though PMT is solar blind, it can still see some photons in visible region and the problem is worse with 297.75nm. It was observed that when the fundamental light at 296.75 nm passed 15 cm away from the PMT’s sensitive area, the detector still registered a significant background signal, as shown in Fig.4.5a. This indicates that the PMT exhibits some residual sensitivity to near-UV wavelengths, requiring additional filtering to suppress unwanted background photons.

To address this issue, a VUV bandpass filter FN147-N-1D from Acton Optics was implemented. This filter features a narrow transmission window, effectively removing the background from the fundamental light while allowing VUV photons to pass through. Figure 4.4 presents the transmission characteristics of this filter, demonstrating its ability to isolate the desired wavelength range. After placing one such filters in front of the PMT, the background signal was completely eliminated, as shown in Fig.4.5b. Figure 4.6 shows the PMT and VUV transmissive filters kept beside each other and also with VUV filter in front

Figure 4.3: PMT signal traces. (a) A typical single-photon pulse from the photomultiplier tube (PMT), with a pulse width of approximately 50 ns and a peak negative amplitude of around -60 mV. (b) Signal recorded under ambient light conditions, showing occasional detection of a few photons (typically 1–2 events per millisecond).

of PMT.

Figure 4.4: Transmission characteristics of the **FN147-N-1D** VUV bandpass filter as provided by Acton Optics. The filter exhibits a peak transmission of approximately 17% at 148 nm, which corresponds to the target VUV wavelength. The transmission rapidly decreases for longer wavelengths and approaches zero beyond 240 nm, effectively blocking unwanted UV and visible light.

For photon counting, a threshold-based detection system is required. The PMT pulses, observed on an oscilloscope, exhibited a typical pulse width of ~ 50 ns and a pulse depth of approximately -60 mV. If a system can register a count whenever the signal crosses a predefined voltage threshold—such as -40 mV—it enables the counting of individual photon events.

(a) PMT signal with 296.75 nm laser **without** filters. (b) PMT signal with 296.75 nm laser **with** filters.

Figure 4.5: Effect of a **FN147-N-1D** VUV-transmissive filter on the PMT signal. (a) Without the filter, the photomultiplier tube (PMT) registers a high background signal, mainly due to residual UV light from the fundamental. (b) With a single VUV-transmissive filter in place, this background is effectively suppressed, enabling selective detection of VUV photons.

To achieve this, a photon counter **MCPC618** from Vertilon Corporation was employed, capable of registering a count whenever the signal exceeded a specified threshold. However, due to very short pulse width, the photon counter perceives the signal amplitude as slightly reduced compared to its actual value. As a result, if a threshold of 40 mV is set, pulses that are truly 40 mV deep may not always be registered.

To correct for this discrepancy, the photon counter was calibrated for 50 ns pulse widths using a function generator (**MFG-2160MR**) from GW Instekt. The calibration procedure involved applying pulses with a fixed width of 50 ns, rise and fall times of 10 ns, and a frequency of 1 MHz. Given this frequency, the expected number of pulses within a count period of 1 ms is 1000 pulses.

The count period refers to the time window over which the photon counter registers and accumulates counts. The working threshold value is defined as the threshold voltage at which the photon counter accurately registers all 1000 expected counts during the count period.

Table 4.1 summarizes the calibrated working threshold values across the required voltage range.

With a set threshold value of -18 mV on the photon counter—equivalent to setting a threshold of -40 mV (see table 4.1) for the actual signal—The number of registered counts without any filter was measured to be 276.33 ± 0.31 counts/ms. Introducing a single VUV filter reduced the count rate dramatically to 0.03 ± 0.00 counts/ms, achieving an extinction ratio of 10^{-4} , which aligns with expectations. Adding a second filter did not significantly

(a) PMT mounted on its holder. The red arrow indicates the PMT; the black arrow points to the adjacent VUV transmissive filters.

(b) PMT mounted with the VUV filter placed directly in front for suppression of background UV light.

Figure 4.6: Photographs of the CsI head-on PMT mounted on its holder, shown with and without the VUV filter.

improve background suppression but would further reduce the detected VUV signal by a factor of ~ 2 , due to the 21% transmission of each filter at the target wavelength. Consequently, the use of a single VUV filter is expected to be sufficient for effective background suppression while maximizing VUV photon detection.

To estimate the minimum detectable power level at 148.3 nm, we analyze the statistical significance of a weak signal in the presence of dark counts. With the VUV filter in place, the measured dark count rate of the PMT is approximately 30 counts/s, which sets the noise floor.

Shot noise arises due to the discrete and random nature of photon detection. It is a fundamental noise source in photon-counting measurements and follows Poissonian statistics. For a process with an average number of counts N in an integration time T , the standard deviation is given by:

$$\sigma(N) = \sqrt{N}.$$

The corresponding standard deviation in terms of the count rate $R = N/T$ is:

$$\sigma(R) = \frac{\sqrt{N}}{T} = \frac{\sqrt{R \cdot T}}{T} = \frac{\sqrt{R}}{\sqrt{T}}.$$

Assuming an averaging time of $T = 1$ s, the standard deviation in the dark count rate due to shot noise becomes:

$$\sigma(R_{\text{dark}}) = \frac{\sqrt{30}}{1 \text{ s}} \approx 5.5 \text{ counts/s}.$$

A signal is considered statistically significant if it exceeds the background fluctuation

Voltage of applied signal(mV)	Working threshold value
-15	-5
-20	-8
-25	-10
-30	-13
-35	-16
-40	-18
-50	-24
-60	-29
-100	-51

Table 4.1: Calibration of the photon counter using 50 ns electrical pulses. The table shows the relationship between the applied pulse peak voltage and the minimum threshold setting at which the photon counter reliably registers 1000 counts per 1 ms gate window. Calibration pulses were generated using a GW Instek **MFG-2160MR** function generator with a fixed width of 50 ns, 10 ns rise and fall times, and a 1 MHz repetition rate. This procedure allows determination of the effective detection threshold for voltage pulses simulating photon events.

by at least three times the standard deviation, i.e.,

$$R_{\text{signal}} = 3 \times \sigma(R_{\text{dark}}) = 3 \times 5.5 \text{ counts/s} = 16.5 \text{ counts/s}.$$

This is the minimum signal count rate that can be reliably detected in background fluctuation for 1 s integration time.

To convert this into the corresponding optical power, we use the quantum efficiency (QE) of the PMT at 148.3 nm, which is 12%, and the transmission (T) of the VUV filter, which is 21%. The overall detection efficiency is:

$$\eta = \text{QE} \times T = 0.12 \times 0.21 = 0.0252.$$

To register 16.5 detected photons per second, the required number of incident photons is:

$$N_{\text{input}} = \frac{16.5 \text{ counts/s}}{\eta} = \frac{16.5 \text{ counts/s}}{0.0252} \approx 654.76 \text{ photons/s}.$$

The energy of a single photon at 148.3 nm is:

$$E_{\text{photon}} = \frac{hc}{\lambda} = \frac{6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \cdot 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s}}{148.3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}} \approx 1.34 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J}.$$

Thus, the corresponding minimum detectable optical power is:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\min} &= 654.76 \text{ photons/s} \times 1.34 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J/photon} \\ &= 8.78 \times 10^{-16} \text{ W} = 0.88 \text{ fW}. \end{aligned}$$

This sets the detection sensitivity limit of the current setup to approximately 0.88 fW at 148.3 nm, assuming a 1 s averaging time and background limited performance. The sensitivity can improve with longer integration times, as shot noise scales with $1/\sqrt{T}$, provided other noise sources remain negligible.

This detection system, integrating a PMT in single-photon counting mode, a photon counter for precise readout, and a VUV filter for background suppression, has been successfully implemented. It will provide a reliable method for detecting low-intensity VUV signals in future high-precision VUV spectroscopy experiments.

Chapter 5

Summary

This thesis presents the progress towards the development of a continuous-wave vacuum ultraviolet (VUV) laser at 148.3 nm for the excitation of the thorium-229m nuclear isomeric transition. The research focused on achieving phase matching essential for second-harmonic generation (SHG), optical cavity stabilization for the enhancement cavity using the Hänsch-Couillaud technique, and the design of a VUV detection system. The exploration of order-disorder poling in BMF crystals may offer an alternative approach to achieving phase matching, compared to conventional techniques such as birefringent or quasi-phase matching used in established nonlinear crystals, essential for generating the required 148.3 nm light. The Hänsch-Couillaud cavity locking technique successfully stabilized the optical cavity, which will ensure enhanced SHG output. Additionally, the VUV detection system, using a Hamamatsu photomultiplier tube (PMT) and single-photon counting, will help in effectively detecting low-power VUV radiation, with VUV transmissive filters minimizing background noise. This work contributes to the broader effort of developing continuous-wave lasers for precision applications in quantum metrology, particularly for the realization of thorium-229m-based nuclear clocks.

Appendix A

A.1 Refractive Indices and poling period Calculations

This section is based on [Vílora 09] unless stated otherwise. In anisotropic nonlinear crystals such as BMF, the refractive index varies with direction and is typically reported along the crystallographic a , b , and c axes. These directional refractive indices play a critical role in determining phase matching conditions for second-harmonic generation (SHG).

Table A.1 presents the refractive indices at the fundamental wavelength $\lambda_w = 296.75 \text{ nm}$ and the second-harmonic wavelength $\lambda_{2w} = 148.375 \text{ nm}$ for each crystallographic axis:

Table A.1: Calculated refractive indices along different crystallographic axes using Sellmeier coefficients reported in [Vílora 09].

Axis / Wavelength	$n(296.75 \text{ nm})$	$n(148.375 \text{ nm})$
n_a	1.4968	1.6540
n_b	1.4707	1.6191
n_c	1.4895	1.6477

In the case of Barium Magnesium Fluoride (BMF), crystal symmetry permits five non-zero elements in the second-order nonlinear susceptibility tensor: d_{31} , d_{32} , d_{33} , d_{24} , and d_{15} . The corresponding values of these nonlinear coefficients, taken from [Vílora 09], are listed in Table A.2.

Table A.2: Nonlinear coefficients of BMF

Coefficient	d_{31}	d_{32}	d_{33}	d_{24}	d_{15}
BMF (pm/V)	0.021	0.039	0.015	0.021	0.021

However, when quasi-phase matching (QPM) is implemented by poling along the crystallographic a - or b -axis, the periodic domain structure constrains light propagation along

the poling direction. Consequently, both the fundamental and second-harmonic waves must be polarized in the plane orthogonal to the poling direction.

Under these conditions, only the nonlinear coefficients d_{31} , d_{32} , and d_{33} are accessible for second-harmonic generation (SHG). These correspond to specific polarization configurations, where the first two indices denote the polarization directions of the fundamental light and the third denotes the polarization of the generated second-harmonic wave:

- d_{32} : **bbc** configuration — two photons polarized along the b -axis generate a second-harmonic photon polarized along the c -axis.
- d_{33} : **ccc** configuration — two photons polarized along the c -axis generate a second-harmonic photon also polarized along the c -axis.
- d_{31} : **aac** configuration — two photons polarized along the a -axis generate a second-harmonic photon polarized along the c -axis.

These tensor components define the interaction geometry in QPM-based SHG using BMF, with the highest nonlinear coefficient being d_{32} , making the **bbc** configuration particularly attractive. However it can be seen from table A.3 that poling period is smallest for this configuration making it practically difficult to achieve.

To derive an expression for poling period for QPM we start from the quasi-phase matching condition (eq. 2.22):

$$\Delta k = k_{2\omega} - 2k_{\omega} = \frac{2\pi m}{\Lambda}, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $k_{2\omega}$ and k_{ω} are the wavevectors at the second-harmonic and fundamental frequencies, respectively, and m is the QPM order. The wavevector is related to the refractive index n and wavelength λ in vacuum by:

$$k = \frac{2\pi n}{\lambda}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Substituting the wavevectors into eq. A.1 we obtain:

$$\frac{n_{2\omega}}{\lambda_{2\omega}} - \frac{2n_{\omega}}{\lambda_{\omega}} = \frac{m}{\Lambda} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Rearranging the equation gives the expression for the QPM poling period (Λ):

$$\Lambda = \frac{m}{\frac{n_{2\omega}}{\lambda_{2\omega}} - \frac{2n_{\omega}}{\lambda_{\omega}}}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Table A.3: Poling periods and domain widths for different nonlinear tensor configurations and QPM orders.

Configuration	QPM Order	n_w	n_{2w}	Period (μm)	Domain Width (μm)
d ₃₂ -bbc	1	1.4707	1.6477	0.8382	0.4191
	3			2.5147	1.2574
	5			4.1912	2.0956
d ₃₃ -ccc	1	1.4895	1.6477	0.9379	0.4689
	3			2.8137	1.4069
	5			4.6894	2.3447
d ₃₁ -aac	1	1.4968	1.6477	0.9834	0.4917
	3			2.9501	1.4751
	5			4.9169	2.4585

Appendix B

B.1 Calculation of single pass conversion efficiency for BMF

To estimate the second-harmonic output from a single pass through the nonlinear crystal, we use a formulation based on the Boyd-Kleinman theory for second-harmonic generation with focused Gaussian beams[Boyd 68]. The single-pass SHG power is given by:

$$P_{\text{SHG}} = \left(\frac{2\omega_1^2 d^2 L_c k_1}{\pi \epsilon_0 c^3 n_1^2 n_2} \cdot P_1^2 \right) \cdot h_{\text{SHG}}(\sigma, \xi, B), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where ω_1 is the angular frequency of the fundamental beam, d is the nonlinear coefficient being used, L_c is the crystal length, k_1 is the wavevector at the fundamental frequency, P_1 is the power of fundamental beam, and n_1 and n_2 are the refractive indices at the fundamental and second-harmonic wavelengths, respectively. The focusing function $h_{\text{SHG}}(\sigma, \xi, B)$ encapsulates the impact of confocal focusing (ξ), spatial walk-off (σ), and phase mismatch, and is evaluated numerically.

The function $h_{\text{SHG}}(\sigma, \xi, B)$ is given by[Daniel 20]:

$$h_{\text{SHG}}(\sigma, \xi, B) = \frac{1}{4\xi} \int_{-\xi}^{+\xi} d\tau_1 \int_{-\xi}^{+\xi} d\tau_2 \frac{e^{i\sigma(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \cdot e^{-\frac{B^2(\tau_1 - \tau_2)^2}{\xi}}}{(1 + i\tau_1)(1 - i\tau_2)}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

with the parameters defined as:

- $\Delta k = 2k_1 - k_2$: wavevector mismatch.
- $\sigma = \frac{b\Delta k}{2}$: normalized phase mismatch parameter.
- $B = \frac{\rho\sqrt{L_c k_1}}{2}$: walk-off parameter, where ρ is the walk-off angle of the crystal.
- $b = \omega_0^2 k_1$: confocal parameter, where ω_0 is the waist of the Gaussian beam.
- $\xi = \frac{L_c}{b}$: focusing parameter, i.e., the ratio of the crystal length to the confocal parameter.

In our experimental configuration, the Gaussian beam waist is $\omega_0 = 44 \mu\text{m}$, and the crystal length is $L_c = 5 \text{ mm}$ if poling is done parallel to b - axis, resulting in a focusing parameter $\xi \approx 0.122$. Assuming no spatial walk-off ($B = 0$) and operating at the optimal phase mismatch (σ) for maximum conversion, the Boyd–Kleinman focusing function evaluates to $h(\sigma, \xi, B) = 0.121$. Using the largest nonlinear coefficient available in BMF, $d_{32} = 0.039 \text{ pm/V}$, and a fundamental pump power of $P_1 = 0.3 \text{ W}$, we calculate the single-pass SHG output power to be:

$$P_{\text{SHG}} = 5.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W}.$$

Table B.1 summarizes the estimated single-pass SHG output powers for various QPM orders and crystal configurations, assuming ideal phase matching and no spatial walk-off.

These low conversion efficiencies highlights the necessity of cavity enhancement, as discussed in the chapter 3.

Table B.1: Estimated SHG output power for different QPM orders and crystal configurations.

Config.	L_c (mm)	ξ	σ	$h(\sigma, \xi, B)$	QPM Order	P_{SHG} (W)
bbc ($d_{32} = 0.039 \text{ pm/V}$)	5	0.122	0.997	0.121	1	5.30×10^{-8}
					3	5.89×10^{-9}
					5	2.12×10^{-9}
					7	1.08×10^{-9}
					9	6.55×10^{-10}
					11	4.38×10^{-10}
aac ($d_{31} = 0.021 \text{ pm/V}$)	10	0.244	0.988	0.239	1	5.85×10^{-8}
					3	6.50×10^{-9}
					5	2.34×10^{-9}
					7	1.19×10^{-9}
					9	7.21×10^{-10}
					11	4.84×10^{-10}

Bibliography

- [Arvanitaki 15] Asimina Arvanitaki, Junwu Huang & Ken Van Tilburg. *Searching for dilaton dark matter with atomic clocks*. Phys. Rev. D, vol. 91, page 015015, Jan 2015.
- [Asenbaum 11] Peter Asenbaum & Markus Arndt. *Cavity stabilization using the weak intrinsic birefringence of dielectric mirrors*. Optics letters, vol. 36 19, pages 3720–2, 2011.
- [Beck 07] B. R. Beck, J. A. Becker, P. Beiersdorfer, G. V. Brown, K. J. Moody, J. B. Wilhelmy, F. S. Porter, C. A. Kilbourne & R. L. Kelley. *Energy Splitting of the Ground-State Doublet in the Nucleus ^{229}Th* . Phys. Rev. Lett., vol. 98, page 142501, Apr 2007.
- [Berceau 10] Paul Berceau, Mathilde Fouché, Rémy Battesti, Franck Bielsa, Julien Mauchain & C Rizzo. *Dynamical behaviour of birefringent Fabry–Perot cavities*. Applied Physics B, vol. 100, pages 803–809, 2010.
- [Bir 97] *Stabilization of an optical cavity containing a birefringent element*. Optics Communications, vol. 140, no. 4, pages 285–288, 1997.
- [Born 19] Max Born & Emil Wolf. *Principles of Optics*. 2019.
- [Boyd 68] G. D. Boyd & D. A. Kleinman. *Parametric Interaction of Focused Gaussian Light Beams*. Journal of Applied Physics, vol. 39, no. 8, pages 3597–3639, 07 1968.
- [Breskin 96] A Breskin. *CsI UV photocathodes: history and mystery*. Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section A: Accelerators, Spectrometers, Detectors and Associated Equipment, vol. 371, no. 1, pages 116–136, 1996. Proceedings of the Second International Workshop on Ring Imaging Cherenkov Detectors.

- [Buchter 01] Scott C. Buchter, Tianyuan Fan, Varda Liberman, John J. Zayhowski, Max F. Rothschild, Aguiar Cassanho, Hans P. Jenssen, Emily J. Mason & John H. Burnett. *Periodically poled BaMgF₄ for ultraviolet frequency generation*. The 15th Annual Meeting of the IEEE Lasers and Electro-Optics Society, vol. 1, pages 131–132 vol.1, 2001.
- [Campbell 12] C. J. Campbell, A. G. Radnaev, A. Kuzmich, V. A. Dzuba, V. V. Flambaum & A. Derevianko. *Single-Ion Nuclear Clock for Metrology at the 19th Decimal Place*. Phys. Rev. Lett., vol. 108, page 120802, Mar 2012.
- [Daniel 20] John R. Daniel, Shan-Wen Tsai & Boerge Hemmerling. *Analytical approximation of the second-harmonic conversion efficiency*. Applied optics, vol. 59 28, pages 9010–9014, 2020.
- [Drever 83] Ronald W. P. Drever, John L. Hall, Frank V. Kowalski, J. Hough, G. M. Ford, A. J. Munley & H. Ward. *Laser phase and frequency stabilization using an optical resonator*. Applied Physics B, vol. 31, pages 97–105, 1983.
- [Elwell 24] R. Elwell, Christian Schneider, Justin Jeet, Jack Terhune, Harry W. T. Morgan, Anastassia N. Alexandrova, H.B. Tran Tan, Andrei Derevianko & E. R. Hudson. *Laser Excitation of the $\{229\}Th$ Nuclear Isomeric Transition in a Solid – State Host*. Physical review letters, vol. 1331, page 013201, 2024.
- [Fiedler 93] K. Fiedler, S. Schiller, R. Paschotta, P. Kürz & J. Mlynek. *Highly efficient frequency doubling with a doubly resonant monolithic total-internal-reflection ring resonator*. Opt. Lett., vol. 18, no. 21, pages 1786–1788, Nov 1993.
- [Flambaum 06] V. V. Flambaum. *Enhanced effect of temporal variation of the fine structure constant and the strong interaction in $229Th$* . Physical review letters, vol. 97 9, page 092502, 2006.
- [Francois 71] G. E. Francois, F. M. Libreht & J. J. Engelen. *Mode Matching with a Single Thin Lens*. Appl. Opt., vol. 10, no. 5, pages 1157–1159, May 1971.
- [Hamamatsu 17] Hamamatsu. *Basic principle of Photomultiplier Tubes*. In Photomultiplier tubes, Basics and Applications, 2017.

- [Hannig 18] S. Hannig, J. Mielke, J. A. Fenske, M. Misera, N. Beev, C. Ospelkaus & P. O. Schmidt. *A highly stable monolithic enhancement cavity for second harmonic generation in the ultraviolet*. Review of Scientific Instruments, vol. 89, no. 1, page 013106, 01 2018.
- [Hänsch 80] Theodor W. Hänsch & Bernard Couillaud. *Laser frequency stabilization by polarization spectroscopy of a reflecting reference cavity*. Optics Communications, vol. 35, pages 441–444, 1980.
- [Helmcke 82] J. Helmcke, S. A. Lee & J. L. Hall. *Dye laser spectrometer for ultra-high spectral resolution: design and performance*. Appl. Opt., vol. 21, no. 9, pages 1686–1694, May 1982.
- [Helmer 94] R. G. Helmer & C. W. Reich. *An excited state of ^{229}Th at 3.5 eV*. Phys. Rev. C, vol. 49, pages 1845–1858, Apr 1994.
- [Herr 23] Simon J. Herr, Hirokichi Tanaka, Ingo Breunig, Matthias Bickermann & Frank Kühnemann. *Fanout periodic poling of BaMgF₄ crystals*. Optical Materials Express, 2023.
- [Honda 09] Y. Honda, H. Shimizu, M. Fukuda, T. Omori, J. Urakawa, K. Sakaue, H. Sakai & N. Sasao. *Stabilization of a non-planar optical cavity using its polarization property*. Optics Communications, vol. 282, no. 15, pages 3108–3112, 2009.
- [Kraemer 22] Sandro Kraemer, Janni Moens, Michail Athanasakis-Kaklamanakis, Silvia Bara, Kjeld Beeks, P. Chhetri, Katerina Chrysalidis, Arno Claessens, Thomas Elias Cocolios, João G. M. Correia, Hilde De Witte, Rafael Ferrer, Sarina Geldhof, Reinhard Heinke, Niyusha Hosseini, Marc Huyse, Ulli Köster, Yu. A. Kudryavtsev, Mustapha Laatiaoui, Răzvan Lică, Goele Magchiels, Vlad Constantin Manea, Clement Merckling, Lino M. C. Pereira, Sebastian Raeder, Thorsten Schumm, Simon Sels, Peter G. Thirolf, Shandirai Malven Tunhuma, Paul Van den Bergh, Piet Van Duppen, André Vantomme, Matthias Verlinde, Renan Villarreal & Ulrich Wahl. *Observation of the radiative decay of the ^{229}Th nuclear clock isomer*. Nature, vol. 617, pages 706 – 710, 2022.
- [Kroger 76] L.A. Kroger & C.W. Reich. *Features of the low-energy level scheme of ^{229}Th as observed in the α -decay of ^{233}U* . Nuclear Physics A, vol. 259, no. 1, pages 29–60, 1976.

- [Ludlow 15] Andrew D. Ludlow, Martin M. Boyd, Jun Ye, E. Peik & P. O. Schmidt. *Optical atomic clocks*. Rev. Mod. Phys., vol. 87, pages 637–701, Jun 2015.
- [Mason 02] Elliott J. Mason. *Applications of optical parametric downconversion: I. Self-phase locking, II. Generation of entangled photon pairs in periodically-poled lithium niobate*. 2002.
- [Nakazato 16] Tomoharu Nakazato, Isao Ito, Yohei Kobayashi, Xiaoyang Wang, Chuangtian Chen & Shuntaro Watanabe. *Phase-matched frequency conversion below 150 nm in KBe₂BO₃F₂*. Opt. Express, vol. 24, no. 15, pages 17149–17158, Jul 2016.
- [New 11] Geoffrey New. *Introduction to Nonlinear Optics: Frontmatter*. 2011.
- [Nikogosyan 91] David N. Nikogosyan. *Beta barium borate (BBO)*. Applied Physics A, vol. 52, pages 359–368, 1991.
- [Patimisco 17] Pietro Patimisco, Angelo Sampaolo, Frank K. Tittel & Vincenzo Spagnolo. *Mode matching of a laser-beam to a compact high finesse bow-tie optical cavity for quartz enhanced photoacoustic gas sensing*. Sensors and Actuators A-physical, vol. 267, pages 70–75, 2017.
- [Peik 03] E. Peik & Chr. Tamm. *Nuclear laser spectroscopy of the 3.5 eV transition in Th-229*. Europhysics Letters, vol. 61, no. 2, page 181, jan 2003.
- [Peik 20] Ekkehard Peik, Thorsten Schumm, Marianna S. Safronova, Adriana Pálffy, Johannes Weitenberg & Peter G. Thirolf. *Nuclear clocks for testing fundamental physics*. Quantum Science & Technology, vol. 6, 2020.
- [Seiferle 17] Benedict Seiferle, Lars C. von der Wense & Peter G. Thirolf. *Lifetime Measurement of the ²²⁹Th Nuclear Isomer*. Physical review letters, vol. 1184, page 042501, 2017.
- [Seiferle 19] Benedict Seiferle, Lars C. von der Wense, Pavlo V. Bilous, Ines Amersdorffer, Christoph Lemell, Florian Libisch, Simon Stellmer, Thorsten Schumm, Christoph Emanuel Düllmann, Adriana Pálffy & Peter G. Thirolf. *Energy of the ²²⁹Th nuclear clock transition*. Nature, vol. 573, pages 243 – 246, 2019.

- [Shao 20] Mingchuan Shao, Fei Liang, Haohai Yu & Huaijin Zhang. *Pushing periodic-disorder-induced phase matching into the deep-ultraviolet spectral region: theory and demonstration*. Light, Science & Applications, vol. 9, 2020.
- [Stadnik 15] Yevgeny V. Stadnik, Benjamin M. Roberts, Victor V. Flambaum & Vladimir A. Dzuba. *Searching for Scalar Dark Matter in Atoms and Astrophysical Phenomena: Variation of Fundamental Constants*. arXiv: High Energy Physics - Phenomenology, 2015.
- [Thirolf 19] Peter G. Thirolf, Benedict Seiferle & Lars der Wense. *Improving Our Knowledge on the ^{229m}Th Isomer: Toward a Test Bench for Time Variations of Fundamental Constants*. Annalen der Physik, vol. 531, 2019.
- [Thirolf 24] Peter G. Thirolf, Sandro Kraemer, Daniel Moritz & Kevin Scharl. *The thorium isomer ^{229m}Th : review of status and perspectives after more than 50 years of research*. The European Physical Journal. Special Topics, vol. 233, pages 1113 – 1131, 2024.
- [Tiedau 24] J. Tiedau, M. V. Okhapkin, K. Zhang, Johannes Thielking, G. Zitzer, E. Peik, Fabian Schaden, T. Pronebner, I. Morawetz, L. Toscani De Col, F. Schneider, Adrian Leitner, M. Pressler, Georgy A. Kazakov, Kjeld Beeks, Tomas Sikorsky & Thorsten Schumm. *Laser Excitation of the Th-^{229} Nucleus*. Physical review letters, vol. 132 18, page 182501, 2024.
- [Vílora 09] Encarnación G. Vílora, Kiyoshi Shimamura, Keiji Sumiya & Hiroyuki Ishibashi. *Birefringent- and quasi phase-matching with BaMgF_4 for vacuum-UV/UV and mid-IR all solid-state lasers*. Opt. Express, vol. 17, no. 15, pages 12362–12378, Jul 2009.
- [von der Wense 16] Lars von der Wense, Benedict Seiferle, Mustapha Laatiaoui, Jürgen B. Neumayr, Hans-Jörg Maier, H-F. Wirth, Ch. Mokry, Jörg Runke, Klaus Eberhardt, Christoph Emanuel Düllmann, Norbert Trautmann & Peter G. Thirolf. *Direct detection of the ^{229}Th nuclear clock transition*. Nature, vol. 533, pages 47–51, 2016.
- [von der Wense 20] Lars von der Wense & Benedict Seiferle. *The ^{229}Th isomer: prospects for a nuclear optical clock*. Eur. Phys. J. A, vol. 56, no. 11, page 277, 2020.

- [Xiao 24] Huaifeng Xiao & Michael J. Damzen. *High-efficiency 5-watt wavelength-tunable UV output from an Alexandrite laser*. Applied Physics B, 2024.
- [Zhang 17] Xiang Zhang, Yijun Zhang, Yunsheng Qian, Cheng Feng, Jingzhi Zhang, Yunlong Jiang & Zhiyun Pan. *Spectral response characteristics of transmission-mode alkali telluride photocathodes working from vacuum-ultraviolet to ultraviolet band*. Journal of Vacuum Science and Technology B: Nanotechnology and Microelectronics, vol. 35, no. 6, 2017. Cited by: 6.
- [Zhang 20] Ling Zhang, Min Zhang, Lirong Wang, Xudong Chen, Jiahao Jiao, Shilie Pan, Guangxin Tang, Xingwang Zhang, Zhaoyang Chen & Xin Zhang. *A 355 nm ultraviolet femtosecond laser through second harmonic generation using K3B6O10Br nonlinear optical crystal*. Optical Materials, vol. 107, page 110088, 2020.
- [Zhang 24] Chuankun Zhang, Tian Ooi, Jacob S. Higgins, John F Doyle, Lars C. von der Wense, Kjeld Beeks, Adrian Leitner, Georgy A. Kazakov, Peng Li, Peter G. Thirolf, Thorsten Schumm & Jun Ye. *Frequency ratio of the ^{229m}Th nuclear isomeric transition and the ^{87}Sr atomic clock*. Nature, vol. 633 8028, pages 63–70, 2024.
- [Zheng 20] Wei Zheng, Lemin Jia & Feng Huang. *Vacuum-Ultraviolet Photon Detections*. iScience, vol. 23, 2020.